

TRANSFORMATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES

FOR
**PEOPLE
OCEAN
PLANET**

**MARINE ENERGY &
TRANSPORTATION**

Blue Climate Initiative

This publication was commissioned by the Blue Climate Initiative (BCI), which accelerates ocean-related strategies, collaborating across a multidisciplinary global community towards a restored and healthy climate; an understood and protected ocean; and resilient, thriving and equitable communities. In 2020 the BCI initiated a holistic process to identify transformational opportunities at the intersection of people, ocean and planet, engaging over sixty world-class scientists and academics. These contributors compiled recommendations across six thematic areas: Health & Well-Being, Food & Nutrition, Marine Energy & Transportation, Mineral & Genetic Resources, Biodiversity & Nature-Based Solutions, and Sustainable Tourism. This publication is part of that series. The BCI is deeply grateful to its authors for their insights and collaboration.

A compendium synthesizing messages across the six Transformational Opportunities papers is available: Fries, L., Everett, J., and Davies, N. (eds.) 2021. Transformational Opportunities for People, Ocean, and Planet. French Polynesia: Blue Climate Initiative, Tetiaroa Society. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4540323>.

For more information about the Blue Climate Initiative, please visit blueclimateinitiative.org or contact info@blueclimateinitiative.org.

The fiscal sponsor for the Blue Climate Initiative is Tetiaroa Society, a US 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization (tetiaroasociety.org).

Suggested citation for this publication:

Transformational Opportunities for Marine Energy & Transportation. Daniel M. Kammen, Jack Chang, Teresa Christopher, Chip Fletcher, Michael Gerrard, Haunani Kane, Heather Leslie, Jessica Reilly-Moman, and Benjamin Wolkon. French Polynesia: Blue Climate Initiative, Tetiaroa Society. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4549891>

ISBN: 978-1-7368426-4-5 (Digital)

© Blue Climate Initiative, Tetiaroa Society 2021
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Transformational Opportunities for Marine Energy & Transportation

Daniel M. Kammen* (University of California, Berkeley, USA), Jack Chang (University of California, Berkeley, USA), Teresa Christopher (TR Christopher LLC, former White House Ocean Policy Advisor, USA), Chip Fletcher (University of Hawai'i, USA), Michael Gerrard (Columbia University, New York City, USA), Haunani Kane (University of Hawai'i, USA), Heather Leslie (University of Maine, USA), Jessica Reilly-Mo-man (University of Maine, USA), and Benjamin Wolkon (Muus Investment Management, NY, USA)

* denotes lead

Executive Summary

Ocean energy and clean energy-based transportation are poised to play a transformative role in both the global economy and in efforts to achieve the 1.5 degree C global warming limit. Indeed, in our assessment, this goal is not achievable without a fundamental reassessment of the relationship of humanity and the ocean. Envisioning and implementing a new relationship between engineered systems, social justice, and environmental restoration open new avenues for the creation and operation of companies and industries, and of the framing of community, and natural management practices.

The interacting threats of climate change, social and racial inequality, and today COVID-19, have generated a renewed recognition of the need to put all economies on paths to sustainable carbon free status by mid-century or before. Progress on clean energy and low-pollution transportation options opens the door to this vision, and enables a healthy, sustainable usage of ocean resources for energy production, transportation, food production, and the improvement of human and ecological health. However, huge economic, political and most notably justice and equity challenges must be addressed and made core to this mission.

With diverse relationships to ocean resources and stewardship around the planet, a key need is for progress toward shared knowledge of best (and at times unsuccessful) practices, shared governance of the ocean as a resource for all, recognizing it as a system that must be holistically managed for community, ocean and planetary health. The needs and rights of marginalized communities are critical to that rebalancing. If such a shared understanding can emerge, the potential to meet significant amounts of human energy, food, and other resource needs while restoring the ocean to a healthy state is possible. Current challenges not only include the sustainable harvest of marine energy, but repair of the damaged state of marine ecosystems, resulting from global warming, toxics and microplastics, and other insults.

The ocean energy potential is vast, with economically viable resources estimated to be far larger than total global current or forecast needs. On a planet that is 71% covered by water, less than 1% of total energy today comes from marine systems, yet forecasts project that by mid-century up to 35% of total energy for stationary power and transportation

in a carbon-free world could be derived from the sustainable management of marine resources. The long-term challenges to marine energy are likely not technical, but are instead those of balancing biodiversity, human well-being, meaningful participation and governance.

In total 6.1 GW of new off-shore wind energy capacity was added around the world in 2019, making it the best year in history for that global industry. The pace of growth is even more staggering. Off-shore wind was 1% of global wind installations by capacity in 2009, but by 2019 offshore wind had grown to over 10% of total global wind installations¹. By the end of this decade, however, off-shore wind could be a leading source of energy generation. As examples, Ireland and the UK have set aggressive clean energy goals of meeting 70% or more of total energy needs from renewables. These goals are dependent on marine energy playing a vastly expanded role from where each nation is today². New York and California and Japan each plan on 10 GW or more of off-shore wind by the end of the decade, meeting 25% or more of statewide and national energy needs³. Recent assessments of off-shore potential and economic benefits show that China and Europe – where 30 GW of off-shore wind is already in operation -- could triple that by the end of the decade⁴.

This vast technical potential will require coordination and investment to realize, but it will also require a greatly expanded knowledge ecosystem to integrate community voice and participation, using tools from social justice for an inclusive ocean energy and transport system that also respects cultural diversity and biodiversity protection. As one example, off-shore wind energy -- for electricity, for H₂ generation as a transportation fuel, and as a means of storage for stationary power generation -- is today being undertaken and projected largely as a classic big-industry initiative.

Opportunities exist, however, for expanded roles of community participation, and gender-based and ethnically inclusive applications of justice.

These steps, far from impeding or costing more in the utilization of ocean resources, would enable both an acceleration of the growth of the ocean energy and ocean food industries. Similar to that of large-scale off-shore wind, tidal and wave energy have great potential as well, but with even more direct community impact. Though a small component of the global energy resource mix today, this can become a world-leading model of shared benefits and responsibilities in the decarbonized future.

The expansion of marine energy enables a number of major societal transformations that are not even clearly articulated today, but are also the subject of this assessment. They include: the potential to transform global food-production to begin the healing of terrestrial and marine ecosystems; new avenues to invest and reap the benefits of freshwater ecosystem health; conservation and restoration of Indigenous communities; and the creation of sustainable transportation networks for freight, passengers, and for an eco-approach to travel and tourism.

The Marine Energy & Transportation working group examined the current and potential future state of sustainable and inclusive marine resource management, with a focus around a set of Transformational Opportunities (TOPs). A focus on social justice and equity emerge as core issues and opportunities of each area.

After an introduction to the rapid changes underway and the challenges for sustainable ocean energy and transport solutions, this paper is focused on a set of findings, recommendations, and actionable research, innovation, and economic scale-up opportunities.

1 Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC) Global Off-shore wind report, 2020, <https://gwec.net/global-offshore-wind-report-2020/>

2 <https://www.windpowermonthly.com/article/1694318/ireland-to-miss-2030-climate-clean-energy-target>

3 <https://www.japantimes.co.jp/news/2020/12/16/business/japan-offshore-wind-power/>

4 Harvard and Berkeley studies [each in final peer-review]

Marine Energy & Transportation Transformational Opportunities Explored in this Paper:

1. Empower, quantify and enable transformational ocean management practices consistent with a global Blue New Deal.

Our oceans are in peril today. A holistic approach to ocean energy development and stewardship represents a transformative resource for human health and for biodiversity and well as cultural conservation. This effort requires a shared knowledge base and perspective on the benefits of sustainable and equitable management of marine resources that connects major industrial sectors and Indigenous communities, and empowers ecosystems with rights in a decarbonized global system.

2. Set new goals for ecologically and culturally-informed marine energy scale-up.

Ocean energy is can play a central role in a 100% clean energy economy⁵. Indeed, many experts are now convinced that it is not possible to achieve the mid-century timeline of the 1.5° C Paris Climate Accords without making zero-carbon marine energy a major component of decarbonization plans. International cooperation on environmental and community impact assessments, on trans-boundary project evaluation and design, and on the integration of energy systems (electricity, Hydrogen, Ammonia, etc.) can make this expansion one that enables governments to accelerate their clean energy plans while promoting equity and ocean health. Each of these energy generation, storage, and transportation options require and will directly benefit from community engagement, participation, and profit-sharing. Social justice enables an expanded, lower-cost, and more sustainable marine energy program.

3. Establish and curate an international repository of marine energy projects.

Clean ocean wind, tidal, and wave energy has the potential to transform and enable the needed acceleration of global decarbonization. At present the global learning and implementation process is massively hindered by the lack of information sharing on technological, impact assessment, legal, and community partnership agreements. Powerful examples exist of best practice sharing that dramatically accelerated the rate of innovation and execution of novel industrial pathways⁶. A global open-access repository and learning network is possible. This TOP, which the Blue Climate Initiative could co-curate, represents the single largest step in meeting near and long-term climate, social justice, and biodiversity restoration and conservation goals.

4. Launch an International Advanced Research Projects for Ocean Energy (ARPO-E).

Marine energy and transportation systems can be greatly advanced through shared research and deployment efforts, and afford a means to build equity and marine health into the commercial sector. The expansion of ocean energy research and deployment programs into areas beyond large-scale off-shore wind already exist, and are templates for the scale-up of both national and international partnership programs. US Department of Energy's ARPA-E program now includes SHARKS, which supports efforts like hydrokinetic, tidal, and riverine energy production⁷, the wave power and tidal energy testing program at EMEC, the European Marine Energy Center⁸, and the launch of three tidal and marine energy test centers in China⁹. The cross-fertilization of both technology research and coastal community integration and shared management is a large unmet need, and an opportunity for marine energy to greatly increase its role in societal and resource sustainability goals. Cross-cutting efforts, such as ARPO-food should also be included

5 LiVecchi, et al. (2019) Powering the Blue Economy; *Exploring Opportunities for Marine Renewable Energy in Maritime Markets*.

6 Examples: include efforts to share and innovate in clean energy project management (<https://www.dsireusa.org>); off-grid energy access (<https://www.gogla.org>); best-practice guides for sustainable agriculture (<http://www.fao.org/3/a-ax270e.pdf>); action guides on biodiversity conservation (<https://cites.org/eng/disc/what.php>) among others.

7 Submarine Hydrokinetic and Riverine Kilo-megawatt Systems, <https://arpa-e.energy.gov/technologies/programs/sharks>

8 <http://www.emec.org.uk/services/provision-of-wave-and-tidal-testing/>

9 China opens Shandong, Zhejiang and Guangdong marine energy test centers: <https://www.offshore-energy.biz/china-to-advance-wave-energy-with-three-test-sites/>

in this Blue New Deal framework where technology assessment, cross-sectoral goals of energy, food, biodiversity conservation, and social justice for participating communities are all assessed as co-equal issues with energy generation.

5. Scale up marine hydrogen energy production (H₂) for a zero-carbon transportation sector.

Sustainably produced marine H₂ can play a key role in greening global transportation needs. To fully leverage the green energy options from marine energy centers, the integration of electricity and H₂ production offers a clean, multi-modality and multi-market approach to the sustainable use of marine energy resources. Marine platforms housing electrolyzers are one prospect, as are marine energy systems sending power to shore (via either AC or DC lines), some of which is used for H₂ production. Seawater mining could be co-located at these facilities as well.

6. Prioritize research and partnerships to expand pilot programs that build the zero-carbon marine energy-food nexus.

Integrating marine energy and sustainable ocean-based food production is an investment in healthy oceans and communities. Some assessments include nearly all human food production from marine systems. This would transform the opportunities for communities and nations to re-wild and sustainably manage stressed and degraded terrestrial ecosystems. At the same time, assessment and monitoring of the human and biodiversity implications of this transition are critical. Unless managed with the same holistic Blue New Deal perspective outlined above, the potential to do damage is vast. Nascent yet promising concepts are now emerging of shared monitoring, management and conservation for sustainability and justice of marine protected areas, local and pelagic fish populations, and marine vegetation for human consumption. Biodiversity and cultural sustainability practices must be made central to this research, development, and dissemination enterprise.

We supplement the report with four deep-dive case studies:

- **Appendix 1:** Na Pua Makani: an ongoing lesson in community rights and empowerment
- **Appendix 2:** Vineyard Community Power: a different approach to community engagement
- **Appendix 3:** Marine energy harnessed for health impacts of retiring peaker plants
- **Appendix 4:** Transformational Opportunity: how Hawai'i could leverage air travel for direct air carbon capture

Transformational Opportunities

1. Empower, quantify and enable transformational ocean management based on the principles of a globally inclusive and just Blue New Deal

The concept of a Blue New Deal^{10 11}, has gained important and now very real traction on ecological, sustainable energy, and social justice grounds. Instead of a useful but sometimes vague set of virtues, the components of a Blue New Deal reflect actionable and holistic approaches to safeguarding ocean-based biodiversity and geochemistry, sustainably exploiting its energy potential, and building global linkages while respecting unique cultures.

Ocean protection and energy production must align with the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change and the Paris Agreement, the Convention on Biological Diversity, and the Polluter Pays Principle as set out in the Rio Declaration. Actions must be aligned across ocean-based and land-based activities and ecosystems. Among the operations guidelines identified by the High-Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy (2020):

- **Inclusiveness:** Human rights, gender equality, community and Indigenous Peoples' participation, through their free, prior and informed consent, must be respected and protected.
- **Knowledge:** Ocean management must be informed by the best available science and knowledge, including Indigenous and local knowledge, and aided by innovation and technology.
- **Legality:** The UN Convention on the Law of the Sea is the legal basis for all ocean activities, and existing international ocean commitments must be implemented as a foundation for achieving a sustainable ocean economy.

- **Precaution:** Where there are threats of serious or irreversible damage, lack of full scientific certainty shall not be used as a reason for postponing cost-effective measures to prevent environmental degradation.
- **Protection:** A healthy ocean underpins a sustainable ocean economy. A net gain approach must be applied to ocean uses in order to help sustain or restore the health of the ocean.
- **Resilience:** The resilience of the ocean and ocean economy must be enhanced.
- **Solidarity:** The need for access to finance, technology and capacity building for developing countries, especially Small Island Developing States and Least Developed Countries, must be recognized, taking into account their particular circumstances and vulnerabilities.
- **Sustainability:** The production and harvesting of ocean resources must be sustainable and support resilient ecosystems and future productivity.

These principles define an exceptionally important and hopeful global 'action agenda' that can be seen as a guide for the further recommendations of this report.

Operationally the High-Level Commission¹² emphasized that the ocean is a complex natural system inextricably linked to land-based activities and ecosystems. As a result, we must approach ocean management holistically in order to achieve the vision of protection, production and prosperity. We need a comprehensive approach to sustainably manage 100% of the ocean, starting with coastal and ocean states and working together regionally and globally to safeguard areas beyond national jurisdiction. A sustainable ocean economy puts people at its center, works for everyone, enables human rights, facilitates the equitable distribution of ocean wealth and ensures equality of opportunity for all. It promotes accountable and transparent business practices, addressing labor rights abuses, including those of child labor, forced labor, trafficking and other forms of exploitation.

10 <https://elizabethwarren.com/plans/blue-new-deal>

11 <https://www.greenbiz.com/article/how-blue-new-deal-charts-course-sustainable-sea-change>

12 <https://www.oceanpanel.org/ocean-action/files/transformations-sustainable-ocean-economy-eng.pdf>

These recent, high-level, commission announcements and reporting have made important progress in advancing and coordinating the recognition of the opportunities and responsibilities of sustainable and equitable ocean stewardship. While history will be the only lens through which we can assess how much progress these announcements will launch and accelerate, possibly the most significant advance happened only recently. In January, 2021, US President Biden signed a historic set of executive orders that completely reorient the federal government to an inclusive all-agency climate-smart posture. US Special Presidential Envoy for Climate John Kerry made the historic statement that:

You cannot protect the oceans without solving climate change and you cannot solve climate change without protecting the oceans... The single most important thing we can do is to raise ambition--that's the only way to create a recovery that is both ocean- and climate-smart¹³.

In the sections below we will examine the components of the vast potential for sustainable marine energy and transport in the context of this Blue New Deal framework, referring regularly to the principles identified above as means to reshape the human-ocean relationship for a sustainable, equitable future. It is clear, of course, that these recommended actions are challenging. However, in many of the most effective environ-

mental policies (such as the Clean Air Act in the United States, and the spread of Feed-in Tariffs for clean energy promotion) the focus on a defining *strategy* was challenging at first, but tremendously helpful in persuading diverse interest groups that new approaches were fair, just, and ultimately of collective as well as individual benefit.

2. Set new goals for ecologically and culturally-informed marine energy scale-up

Snapshot: An Industry Undergoing Unprecedented Growth

Offshore wind's technical potential is tremendous, estimated at 36,000 TWh per year for installations in water less than 60 meters deep and within 60 km from shore. For perspective, total global electricity demand is currently 23,000 TWh, likely to double or more by mid-century. Moving further from shore and into deeper waters, floating turbines could unlock enough potential to meet the world's total electricity demand 10 times over¹⁴ (Figure 1). The scale of the resource is, of course, only a start. Tidal and wave energy are smaller in project scale, but have great potential to be integrated into equitable community partnerships. Further, marine energy centers can also become hubs of Hydrogen (H₂) and Ammonia (NH₃) production for energy storage. Further, food production co-lo-

Figure 1: Off-shore energy resources worldwide. Left) Large wind energy resources exist off virtually every heavily populated coastline; Right) Tidal energy resources. Sources: Left: <https://windenergy.dtu.dk/english/>; Right: <https://minesto.com/ocean-energied coastline>.

13 <https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/presidential-actions/2021/01/27/executive-order-on-tackling-the-climate-crisis-at-home-and-abroad/>

14 https://webstore.iea.org/download/direct/2886?filename=offshore_wind_outlook_2019.pdf

cated with wind, tidal, or wave energy offer prospects to relieve stress on land, and are both the subject of Recommendations 5 and 7 of this report, as well as the Food & Nutrition Working Group.

Off-shore energy is currently undergoing dramatic – in fact exponential – growth. Forecasts are that as soon as 2030 off-shore wind and other marine energy (wave, tidal, and ocean thermal) may potentially grow by a *factor of 10 - 100*. This is exceptional, and would exceed the fastest growth rates seen for nuclear power in the 1970s, gas in the 1990s, and solar power today, each of which held records for the fastest changes in the energy industry until the next technological era, and would make marine energy a leading source of total energy in many nations and regions. The challenges that will need to be addressed to sustain this growth, however, are multi-dimensional. Larger and more efficient turbines will be needed, of course, but sustaining this expansion in ways that do not just generate energy and energy storage, but create social equity and justice, and promote and restore ocean health are the true goals of the Blue New Deal.

In the following sections we focus first on off-shore wind, then turn to tidal, wave and ocean thermal energy opportunities. Finally, we will explore the social justice opportunities and then the crossover opportunities between electricity, energy storage, and zero-carbon food production.

Wind resources and technological innovation

Near-shore economically viable wind resources worldwide are vast, in excess of global energy consumption today (~ 23,000 TWh/year). When deep-water (> 50 meter) resources are included, the resource is several times the total global energy consumption forecast for 2050 (~ 50 TWh/year).

The cost reductions seen for offshore wind farms have been driven by technology improvements that have raised capacity factors, as well as by declines in total installed costs, operations and maintenance costs, and the cost of capital as project risk has declined.

Improvement in wind turbine technology is helping to drive down costs. Between 2010 and 2020 the weighted average turbine size for newly commissioned off-

Source: IRENA Renewable Cost Database and Auctions Database.
 Note: Each circle represents an individual project or an auction result where there was a single clearing price at auction. The centre of the circle is the value for the cost of each project on the Y axis. The thick lines are the global weighted average LCOE, or auction values, by year. For the LCOE data, the real WACC is 7.5% for OECD countries and China, and 10% for the rest of the world. The band represents the fossil fuel-fired power generation cost range.

Figure 2: The decline in off-shore wind prices has followed the classic learning curve (Kittner, Lill and Kammen, 2017) of roughly 20% price decline for each doubling in installed capacity. Unlike solar and onshore wind, the progress has been remarkably compressed in time, with the industry going from MW scale pilots to GW sized farms in under a decade. The price decline and performance improvements make off-shore wind directly competitive with other clean energy options, with stronger prospects for continued decline than many other technologies.

shore wind farms increased from 2.9 MW to 8.3 MW, an increase of 184% (Figure 2). The growth in turbine size helps to increase wind farm output. These larger turbines with greater swept areas yield higher capacity factors for the same resource quality. As a result, the global weighted average capacity factor of new offshore wind farms has increased by a third between 2010 and 2020, to 51%. The rate of technological learning in the off-shore wind industry today is on par with the 20% rate seen steadily in solar PV and in on-shore wind over the past decades, but the process has been compressed in time as a result of the massive building spree that is now underway worldwide and planned over the next decade.

Europe:

Europe is the current global leader in marine energy deployment. At the end of 2019 there were 205 GW of installed wind power capacity in Europe: 183 GW on-shore and 22 GW offshore (Table 1, Figure 3). Some of the most aggressive forecasts for the expansion of the off-shore energy industry are staggering, at up to 450 GW of total offshore wind by 2050. This is 20 times more than the 20 GW installed today. If this growth were to take place, on-shore and off-shore wind would supply half of EU energy needs¹⁵. The emphasis here is on meeting multiple different, and complementary energy demands.

Europe’s first marine energy farms – of the coasts of Denmark, the Netherlands, Ireland and the UK is the expansion of the market. Initially built exclusively for electricity, Europe’s wind-farms are now seen as sources of electricity and Hydrogen so that the massive expansion is driven by the demand for renewable electricity, the demand for energy for industry, and as a replacement for petroleum and diesel as EU nations phase out internal combustion engines.

Table 1: Off-shore wind energy in Europe, 2020¹⁶.

Nation	Nation	# of Turbines
Belgium	Belgium	399
Denmark	Denmark	559
Finland	Finland	19
France	France	1
Germany	7,689	1,501
Ireland	25	7
Netherlands	2,620	538
Norway	2	1
Portugal	25	3
Spain	5	1
Sweden	192	80
UK	10,428	2,294

The first European floating wind-farm was launched in January, 2021¹⁷ (Figure 4). This is a significant innovation along several dimensions, each of which open the prospects of significant new innovations and commercial scale-up efforts.

Figure 3: European Off-shore wind farms, 2020. Off-shore wind totals for Europe exceed 22 GW in 2020, with large additional planned projects for each nation¹⁸.

15 <https://etipwind.eu/event/etipwind-workshop-on-450gw-to-deliver-450-gw-of-offshore-wind/>

16 <https://windeurope.org/about-wind/interactive-offshore-maps/>

17 <https://www.tdworl.com/renewables/article/21151449/continental-europes-first-floating-wind-farm>

18 <https://windeurope.org/data-and-analysis/product/european-offshore-wind-farms-map-public/>

Specifically:

- It enables both large size and large numbers of wind turbines to be installed at depths of greater than 50 m;
- Each wind turbine operates on top of a floating platform moored to the seafloor by cables and chains, guaranteeing stability;
- This system eliminates the need for the complex offshore operations involved in building traditional fixed structures, thus reducing its environmental impact; and
- The platform and wind turbine are assembled at port and later towed to their final location.

What this development also speaks to are the many aspects of the ‘S-curve’ of innovation¹⁹ being very active in the marine energy space, with no immediate prospect for the learning curve to ‘flatten’ or to reduce the

relationship of technology deployment with continued cost declines.

The expansion of the European off-shore wind industry is today driven not only by low cost and electricity sales, but also by Hydrogen production. The demand for Hydrogen, in turn is being driven by industrial policy focused on fossil-fuel free industrial parks such as Zero Carbon Humber in the UK²⁰, which will be powered by Hydrogen that is combusted or used in fuel cells. More on this in Section 7.

Figure 4: The first fully floating wind-turbine array installed off the coast of Portugal²¹. Significantly, these tripod platforms enable conventional land-based turbines to be installed at low cost in moored, floating arrays. This innovation both builds industry experience and re-purposes existing industrial capacity.

19 The ‘S-curve’ theory is that each technology exhibits an initial exponential growth phase, followed by a plateau (the ‘S shape’) that stalls industry growth unless a next, successive ‘S’ can be stacked on the first one to continue industry growth and cost declines. Often market or regulatory barriers require attention to enable these next phases of growth even if technological innovation has taken place. The transition to off-shore floating turbines addresses a number of issues that have changed what some experts saw as a plateau in off-shore wind to simply move to a successive stage of innovation and industry growth.

20 <https://www.zerocarbonhumber.co.uk/the-vision/>

21 <https://www.tdworld.com/renewables/article/21151449/continental-europes-first-floating-wind-farm>

China:

Over just the past two years, China's offshore wind power has increased more than any other nation. China accounted for 40% of global added offshore wind capacity in 2019, with a record 2.5 gigawatts (GW) added, 51% more than the previous year. China now has 10 GW installed, 23% of the world's offshore wind capacity²², with plans to increase total off-shore energy production by five-fold to 60 GW by 2030 (Figure 5).

Offshore wind has significant advantages over onshore installation in China. First, China's 18,000 km coastline borders over 3 million square kilometers of ocean suitable for wind power development and receives ample wind. According to a report by the China Renewable Energy Engineering Institute²³ on renewable energy development in China, coastal wind power resources are concentrated on the south-east coast and China's islands where favorable wind regimes provide 300 watts/m² or more. There is an estimated 190 GW

of potential capacity at a height of 100 meters above sea level where water depths are shallow, between 5 and 25 meters – and 320 GW at depths of between 25 and 50 meters. Should China follow the UK model of floating wind farms, the estimates of total capacity are huge, in excess of 800 GW, or 40% of total Chinese energy demand today.

Secondly, China's economic activity is concentrated on its coasts where there is greater demand for power. By contrast, onshore wind generates mainly in the north of the country and needs to be transported long distances to reach consumers. China's 11 coastal provinces account for over 50% of national electricity use²⁴.

Figure 5: Off-shore wind installed in China through 2019. While 7 GW is large on the global stage it is small compared to the 50 GW of additional installation that China plans in the coming years. Most impressive, however, is the consistent set of installations across the coastal provinces, which highlights the benefits of a balanced strategy where all available coastal areas have 'skin in the game'²⁵

²² Most of China's new capacity was added in Jiangsu, Guangdong and Fujian, with Jiangsu accounting for the lion's share – 1.6 GW, 64% of the national total. Guangdong and Fujian added 0.35 GW and 0.2 gigawatts respectively. What is significant about this total is that many of the most attractive sites in terms of population and demand have not even been opened for installation. The growth of the Chinese industry to 60 GW appears if anything, conservative based on demand, cost, and the ease of permitting in the Chinese centrally-planned system.

²³ <http://www.creei.cn/portal/index/welcome.html>

²⁴ <https://chinadialogue.net/en/energy/china-offshore-wind-power-growth/>

²⁵ Ibid.

Other Asia:

Marine energy development is moving rapidly in a number of Asian nations beyond China, with Japan, Korea, Taiwan, and Vietnam all planning significant marine energy development. Japan has a target to install 10 GW of offshore wind capacity by 2030, and it has enacted legislation to take steps to meet this target. The government launched the country's first offshore wind auction for a floating offshore wind farm off the coast of Goto City in June 2020 and the country's first offshore wind auction for fixed-bottom offshore wind farms in November 2020. The tender for fixed-bottom projects will remain open until May 27, 2021 and covers four zones that are located off Akita and Chiba prefectures.

Similarly, South Korea set a target of 12 GW of offshore wind capacity by 2030 in its Renewable Energy 2030 implementation plan announced in 2018. Offshore wind is critical to achieving its new net-zero emissions target by 2050. According to the Global Wind Energy Council, South Korea has installed only 132.5 megawatts of offshore wind capacity currently. It has several floating offshore wind projects in development. With deep water coastlines, South Korea may well take advantage of the innovation now taking place in Europe, but with the significantly larger heavy-industry capacity for rapid construction in Asia.

Vietnam has the potential for over 250 GW of on-shore and over 200 GW of floating offshore wind, according to the 2019 World Bank report *Going Global: Expanding Offshore Wind to Emerging Markets*²⁶. The Vietnamese government is currently evaluating a proposal to extend its feed-in tariff regime by another two years through November 2023, including off-shore wind in the eligible technology categories. The current tariff of 98 US¢ a kilowatt hour to offshore wind projects that reach commercial operation by November 2021. In total these markets are potentially immense, and suggest the forecasts today of the off-shore wind development are if anything, conservative.

²⁶ <https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/energy/publication/expanding-offshore-wind-in-emerging-markets>

²⁷ <https://www.cleanenergyforbiden.com/policysummit>

United States

The United States is perhaps the most dramatically evolving entrant in the marine energy space. Between 2018 and 2020 California, New York, and Delaware have each set state goals for 10 GW of off-shore wind by 2030, with others likely to follow. The scale of this growth literally changes the landscape of clean energy across the country, with two of the three largest energy markets, CA and NY planning to meet 25% or more of forecast demand by 2030 with off-shore wind, that provides no power today. The other large market, Texas has excellent wind potential in the Gulf of Mexico, and has not yet even entered this conversation.

Equally significant, marine energy plays a prominent role in the plans announced by President Biden in a series of January 2021 Executive Orders. It is estimated that by scaling up marine energy, American industry is capable of generating 5 GW of offshore wind power by 2025 followed by 30,000 MW by 2030—enough to power 11 million homes. Conservatively, forecasts are for 200 GW of installed off-shore wind before 2050²⁷.

Central to the Biden Administration transition plan from fossil fuels to renewable energy, offshore wind can deliver immediate job creation during the first term of the Biden-Harris administration while playing a pivotal role in meeting the 100% clean energy by 2035 goal and standing up an enduring new technology sector that could absorb much of the forecast job losses in the oil and gas sectors.

Early administrative actions on the part of the Biden-Harris administration can get construction started on currently-designed projects on the East Coast, while also stimulating new project work on the West Coast, Gulf of Mexico, and Great Lakes, as well as manufacturing in inland and coastal states. States from Massachusetts to Virginia have already put the policies and contracts into place needed to get projects built; they only await federal actions held up by the Trump Administration's Department of the Interior (DOI). Because offshore wind projects are located in federal waters, they rest on DOI's ability to issue the

necessary leases and permits. The early Biden Administration actions are clearly designed to set this build-out into motion, with the estimated benefits beyond clean electricity that are forecast to include:

- More than 80,000 high-paying jobs by 2025, with further expansion continuing to at least through 2035.
- \$17 billion injected into the U.S. economy by 2025, \$108 billion by 2030 and \$166 billion by 2035 for construction, transportation and port-related development.
- Nearly \$2 billion in offshore lease payments are forecast to flow to the U.S. Treasury between 2021 and 2022 alone.

Each of these co-benefits are highly significant for a new administration that is committed to rebuild a COVID-19 damaged economy while shifting from fossil fuels to renewable energy (See Section 6, below).

This explosive growth is literally game-changing, and could both enable aggressive new clean energy goals as well as reshape how we consider the world's oceans. Recent estimates of the economic impact of this level of growth is that almost *one million* new jobs could be created in the off-shore wind industry alone. It is important to recognize that the *scale of growth* that these national assessments and targets encompass are on scale with the largest scale-ups of different energy technologies we have seen in the recent past, notably nuclear in the 1960s-1970s, and gas in the 1980s-90s, or the path that solar is on today. In these terms the rise of marine energy on the global landscape, may be seen as a fourth wave of energy sector evolution, but also raises a range of challenges for the early integration of impact assessments on the environment and of under-resourced, and disadvantaged communities and effective strategies to make justice and long-term sustainability core components and not an afterthought.

The marine non-wind energy resource is far larger than that of wind, but the technical potential is smaller. While off-shore wind is moving towards ultra-large (GW) scale projects, marine energy (the term generally used for non-wind ocean energy) has the potential for smaller-scale community and city-sized resources.

Coastal communities directly encompass 37% of the world's population (and continue to grow) and include 2/3 (two-thirds) of the world's 20 current most populous cities.

US:

The total US wind capacity in 2020 is 114 GW, all of it on-shore. However, the coming decade is likely to be one dominated by the growth in off-shore energy.

The technically recoverable US resource for both off-shore wind and wave energy is tremendous. In the United States, the offshore wind energy potential is over 2,000 GW, and the wave energy potential is over 500 GW, together totaling over twice the current national electricity consumption¹. Despite this potential, today there is only one 5-turbine (30 MW) offshore wind farm and no commercially operating wave energy farms. US off-shore wind energy is rapidly launching, however, with over 40 GW of proposed projects all slated for completion in the next half-decade.

State policies in Maryland, Massachusetts, New Jersey, New York, Rhode Island, and others are vital drivers for the offshore wind industry. These policies will help achieve scale and develop an American supply chain. With stable policy in place, the U.S. could create 83,000 jobs by 2030.

Forecasts for US wind deployment exceed 400 GW by 2050, with a great deal of that total off-shore.

Rest of World:

Off-shore wind and marine energy development is also underway or under discussion in Australia and Latin America, notably in Brazil and Chile, with discussions in Africa. Smaller scale marine energy projects exist or are under development in the Philippines, across the Pacific Island states, and in southeast Asia.

The wider marine energy resource: beyond off-shore wind

So far this assessment has focused on off-shore wind, but the opportunity to take advantage of wave, tidal, and ocean/river current energy as well as ocean thermal (OTEC) technology is very significant. For the United States alone, the estimated economically viable “technical” non-wind resource approaches 40% of total US electricity consumption (Table 2). This is significant for a number of reasons beyond the electricity capacity alone.

First, tidal and wave power are inherently smaller resources not in total theoretical potential, but in terms of near-shore deployable systems. Many of the emerging technologies – from buoys, to mechanical chains, to bottom mounted systems to tethered kites – are in the kW to tens of MW scale – so that their deployment can be integrated into community-scale partnerships. That does not mean that integration issues and true political power and profit sharing will always be pursued, but the scale does lend itself to partnership, not exploitative relationships. After significant challenges in building successful industry-community partnerships between 2000 and 2010, cases of community-based programs where this was indeed successful are becoming increasingly common in Maine²⁸ (USA), British Columbia²⁹ (Canada), and elsewhere.

The lessons from a few tidal, wave, OTEC, and Salt Water Air Conditioning (SWAC) projects³⁰ has been

increasingly positive, but a far greater diversity of projects will be needed to establish both a knowledge base of tidal and wave projects, as well as a database of best practice technical, legal, and other arrangements to facilitate further projects. We explore the need and the opportunity to build such a resource in Section 3. In Section 4, we turn to the diverse set of technologies that have emerged for wave and tidal energy generation, and the benefits of a coordinated research and development pipeline to accelerate the rate of innovation and field testing of both these technologies, and to gain experience in deployment efforts that maximally benefit participating community groups as empowered true partners with developers.

The diversifying technology landscape for off-shore wind

The scale and capacity of the newest generation of off-shore wind turbines is extraordinary compared to even the forecasts made even five years ago. Capital investment in offshore wind has more than tripled over the last decade to \$26 billion, according to the International Energy Agency, the Paris-based forecasting group.

The results of this wave of investment are already appearing. We have previously introduced the novel floating platform technology to adapt on-shore turbines to off-shore systems. A different sort of technology breakthrough was unveiled in late 2020 when GE introduced the 850’ tall GE Haliade-X 13MW turbine

Resource assessment	US marine non-wind energy resource potential
Wave Power	<i>Theoretical:</i> 1,594–2,640 TWh/year <i>Technical:</i> 898–1,229 TWh/year
Tidal Power	<i>Theoretical:</i> 445 TWh/year <i>Technical:</i> 222–334 TWh/year
Ocean currents	<i>Theoretical:</i> 200 TWh/year <i>Technical:</i> 45–163 TWh/year
River currents	<i>Theoretical:</i> 1,381 TWh/year <i>Technical:</i> 120 TWh/year

Table 2: Marine energy resource potential. For reference, approximately 90,000 homes can be powered by 1 TWh/year. For comparison, total US electricity demand in 2019 was 4,200 TWh.

28 <https://umaine.edu/mitchellcenter/road-to-solutions/renewable-energy-from-the-tides/>

29 <https://www.cleanenergybc.org/about/clean-energy-sectors/wave>

30 <https://www.dolfines.com/renewable-study-swac-pipeline-bora-bora-island/>

Figure 6: Source: The new GE Haliade-X 13 MW single turbine

that can power more than 12,000 homes with a single turbine³¹ (Figure 6). This machine where the tip-speed is approaching the speed of sound, represents a breakthrough in single-turbine scale that makes the development of GW-scale farms, or of single turbine projects to power coastal communities far easier to plan and deploy.

Always aware of the need to continue to innovate, Morten Pilgaard Rasmussen, chief technology officer of the offshore wind unit of Siemens Gamesa Renewable Energy, the leading maker of offshore turbines, noted on the ribbon-cutting for the GE Haliade-X, “we

will also reach a plateau; we just don’t know where it is yet”.

Prices and trends; Beyond the LCOE of Marine Energy

As noted above the costs of off-shore wind are falling rapidly, so much so that off-shore wind it is now directly cost-competitive with other clean energy technologies (Table 3 & Figure 7).

Current costs tell only part of the story. Significant valuation benefits and cost reductions are possible by integrating marine energy systems thoughtfully with

Table 3: comparison of least-cost reported marine energy and fossil-fuel energy costs.

Technology	LCOE 2015 (USD/MWh)	LCOE 2030 (USD/MWh)	Reference
Offshore Wind	130 - 450	60 - 190	EIA
Wave Energy	387 - 763	96 - 487	EIA; Sunter et al. 2017
Natural Gas (CCGT)	60 - 140	32 - 98	IEA
Coal	82 - 104	35 - 86	IEA

31 Stanley Reed (2021), “A monster wind turbine is upending an industry,” The New York Times, January 1, 2021. https://www.nytimes.com/2021/01/01/business/GE-wind-turbine.html?action=click&algo=bandit-all-surfaces&block=trending_recirc&fallback=false&impression_id=713602115&impression_id=2a4f1072-4c63-11eb-8bb4-c3d03aa3d4c4&index=2&pgtype=Article®ion=footer&req_id=564411204&surface=most-popular&variant=1_bandit-all-surfaces_daysback_4

Figure 7: Wave and wind combined energy enhances energy yield. Hourly capacity factors for combinations of wave and wind energy (blue), wave and solar energy (red), and solar and wind energy (black) are shown in thin lines. Thick lines show the annual average combined capacity factor for each combination in 2016 in northwest Oregon site.

other energy assets. The options for this are significant, including competing with energy storage when the timing of marine energy fills gaps left by other intermittent renewables, or utilizing energy produced at times of low demand for H₂ or NH₃ production, or by co-locating energy systems such as off-shore wind with tidal and ocean current turbines, or floating solar with wind or by integrating marine energy and ocean food production.

As one example, a number of studies have found that up to 2/3 of offshore wind farm project development costs are mutual to a wave energy project and could be shared (Sunter, et al, 2017). The performance of a combined farm would provide enhanced energy yield, better predictability, and smoothed power output. Preliminary analysis shows improved combined capacity factors to be highest for wind and wave relative to other renewable energy combinations for some locations, as seen in Figure 7. Wave energy is predictable up to 3 days in advance and is more consistent than many other renewable alternatives. As can be seen in the Figure, below, the inter-hour variability in power output is less for a combined farm than a farm composed entirely of wind or wave energy alone. The shadow effect from the placement of the wave energy converters can even provide a milder wave climate for the offshore wind turbines. These benefits may become even more salient as the offshore wind industry trends toward

floating offshore wind platforms, which are of particular interest on the deeper coastlines off the U.S. West Coast with one of the world's largest and most consistent wave energy resources.

The Challenges and Lessons of Social Justice

The history of large projects and colonial governments appropriating the land, water and other resources from Indigenous communities is long and deeply problematic. Coastal people are often directly in harm's way as settler/colonizer groups first ignore then evict Black, Indigenous and People of Color (BIPOC) communities. We provide here two cases in the Appendix, one illustrating a classic battle for community rights as an Indigenous community fights against being overwhelmed with the construction of the Na Pua Makani Windfarm that encroached and dominated a small Oahu community (Appendix 1). Second, we include a far more positive case of direct community engagement and a successful partnership between developer and the local community: the case of Vineyard Wind in New England (Appendix 2).

3. Establish and curate an international repository of marine energy projects

The rapid growth of the marine energy industry has been breathtaking, and opens the prospects for zero-carbon power systems, zero-carbon transportation, and sustainable food production. At the same time, wind, tidal and wave, and the ocean transport sectors are largely uncoordinated, with many jurisdictions finding the need to create from scratch ocean and community protection processes and regulations. Many marine infrastructure projects worldwide encounter significant barriers in their technological, economic, and notably in their legal status with pre-existing communities opposition, challenges over their impact on protected areas, as well as other constraints on their development, operation, profit-sharing and maintenance. A growing body of academic and legal work has identified marine governance issues as one of, or even, the main challenge in transitioning towards sustainable energy futures, and in particular those legal structures that empower disadvantaged communities (Folke, et al., 2005, Kerr, et al., 2015, Lange, et al., 2018).

These lessons are often very difficult for developers in other parts of the world to find and utilize in efforts to learn from ‘best practices’ (and to avoid ‘worst practices’)³².

To guide the design of such a resource, we highlight here a number of past and current holistic data integration efforts that are worth exploring to design this marine sustainability go-to resource and help center.

*The Climate hot map*³³

The climate hot map is a geospatially resolved, interactive, database of climate crises and tipping points that links data on specific, local climate emergencies, with academic papers, relevant local or national legislation,

funding efforts, and other elements of how the data on climate change was transformed into action. Of particular importance for this Marine Energy and Transportation perspective, the hot map integrates across science, legal, economic, and community responses to climate emergencies.

*The 2100 Project: An Atlas for the Green New Deal*³⁴

This geospatially resolved atlas of projects and needs, focused on frontline, poor, and communities of color, provides a resource of individual opportunities and actions to invest in climate- and community-smart projects.

*The OCEANIC Project*³⁵

The OCEANIC Project is a technology-focused effort to make available data on hardware solutions to marine energy and transport challenges with specialized knowledge of the performance, weathering, and corrosion and fouling issues specific to marine infrastructure.

*The European Marine Energy Research Center Wave Devices Database*³⁶

This technology-specific data base brings together data on wave, tidal, mooring and other ocean energy hardware, as well as test-performance data.

*The PRIMRE Marine Renewable Energy Technology Database*³⁷

The PRIMRE Marine Renewable Energy Technology Database provides information on marine and hydrokinetic renewable energy projects, devices, technologies, and organizations in the U.S. and around the world. The database includes information on wave, tidal, current, and ocean thermal energy, various energy conversion technologies, companies active in the field, and development of projects in the water. Each

32 For an excellent high-level database of marine energy legal arrangements, see: <https://tethys.pnnl.gov/regulatory-frameworks-marine-renewable-energy>

33 <https://www.climatehotmap.org/global-warming-solutions/>

34 <https://mcharg.upenn.edu/2100-project-atlas-green-new-deal>

35 <http://oceanic-project.eu/oceanic-project/>

36 <http://www.emec.org.uk/marine-energy/wave-devices/>

37 https://openei.org/wiki/PRIMRE/Databases/Technology_Database

of the pages in this database are linked to one another, creating a rich data structure to explore the relationships between organizations operating in the MRE sector, their projects, technologies being deployed, and the devices that they are developing.

While many sector-specific, searchable data sets exist (although many are not open access), we have been unable to identify a resource that combines technical material on: ocean energy resources; new and emerging marine energy and clean-energy transport technologies; economic assessments; legal document on licensing and siting; data on ecological impacts; data on community acceptance, partnership, or challenges, and on the means to identify and engage with funders. Each of these issues are critical to the scope and envisioned social and ecologically appropriate development that is consistent with the Blue New Deal.

To address this key but often overlooked barrier, we propose that the Blue Climate Initiative take on this role. The curation of open-access data sets that make co-equal the technical, legal, and community-participation would be a huge asset to the evolving marine energy, transport, food, and other marine resource issues.

4. Launch an International Advanced Research Projects for Ocean Energy (ARPO-E)

The distinct technical needs, technological diversity, and range of deployment conditions (including high-latitude temperature extreme, high or low-salinity settings, and the wide range of ecological conditions) all speak to the need for a robust research program focused not only marine energy hardware, but also on ease of maintenance, long-term performance, and the design of management, government, and other shared ownership models. This systems-level diversity is well suited to many of the key lessons from the decade of experience we now have with the ARPA-E program model.

While there have been many assessments of ARPA-E, most summaries of the program's strengths focus on a number of cultural elements.

ARPA-E's approach has focused on identifying off-roadmap, "white space" research, i.e., research that isn't being pursued anywhere else or requires levels of interdisciplinary assessment that is difficult to provide in traditional grant-grantee relationships. Like DARPA, ARPA-E recruits top talent from across the energy space to identify and utilize unique approaches to solve difficult problems. These program directors utilize a workshop process to refine the scope of the programs they pursue. Like a "shark tank" for identifying important research, program directors have to convince not just the agency, but also a multi-disciplinary team of scientists that they've identified a problem worth solving. The bar is, as former ARPA-E Director Dr. Ellen Williams has often noted, "if it works, will it matter?" Once they've settled on a refined program, they fund a portfolio of projects, increasing the chance of success by creating more shots on goal instead of focusing on a specific and predetermined set of technologies that may not end up working.

Empowering program directors in this way – while requiring them to demonstrate that a topic is worth exploring – ensures that instead of a top-down, centrally planned research program, ARPA-E has the flexibility to pursue research targets of opportunity that would be more difficult under traditional institutional arrangements. This approach has been key to ARPA-E's success.

This is particularly needed in the marine energy space where many ideas have been floated, but often without the early-stage investment to take a theoretical design, or a small-scale prototype through both a rigorous technical assessment, but an equally challenging marketing or social benefits analysis.

A focus on early-stage problem definitions and investment

Importantly, ARPA-E focuses on projects that are at times too early in their development to attract private sector funding, or on projects whose benefits occupy several areas and thus may be under-valued with single-metric assessment programs. As the recent National Academy of Sciences Assessment on ARPA-E found³⁸, ARPA-E is funding projects that no one else is funding. This isn't surprising, given the early stage and high-risk nature of the projects they're pursuing. ARPA-E has also demonstrated an ability to accelerate the development of early-stage projects. A Government Accountability Office report found that most ARPA-E funded projects were either at or before proof-of-concept stages. Without ARPA-E's support, they would have either terminated their projects, or taken at least a decade to commercialize them.

An empowered management style

One of the defining features of the ARPA-E program is active management. This hands-on approach means program directors are involved in developing budgets, timelines and milestones that projects must meet to receive continued funding. A unique component of ARPA-E's management toolkit is the use of techno-economic analysis, which helps project innovators identify and anticipate commercialization challenges such as market shifts or manufacturing bottlenecks that could derail their work. Identifying these challenges early in a technology's development helps to avoid the "valley of death" – delays or cost overruns that cause a project to fail. This metric-driven process also means that when projects are underperforming and need to be terminated, these decisions can be made with confidence, ensuring responsible stewardship of taxpayer dollars. This culture of self-evaluation benefits ARPA-E's own management structure as they continually refine internal processes.

Many innovators in the marine energy space have significant experience in other energy areas, but limited background with marine energy, which is often said to be the watery grave of ideas. Indeed, the oft-repeated

axiom is that good ideas wither when one 'adds salt.' With dedicated project managers that push hard for milestones and practical testing, the ARPA-E model can provide the sort of feedback that marine energy projects often need.

Successful programs that emerged from DOE's Advanced Research Projects Agency-Energy model include the Marine Research Inspiring Novel Energy Resources (MARINER) and the SHARKS program.

The SHARKS program seeks to develop new technical pathways to design economically competitive Hydrokinetic Turbines (HKT) for tidal and riverine currents. These renewable energy resources are highly reliable, forecastable, and typically co-located with demand centers. HKTs are suited for both micro-grids that supply energy to remote communities without grid connections and utility-scale grid-connected applications. Despite these attractive qualities, current HKTs are too expensive for deployment due to technical challenges and harsh operational environments. This program seeks to fund new holistic HKT designs to reduce significantly their levelized cost of energy (LCOE). SHARKS encourages the application of control co-design (CCD), co-design (CD), and designing for operation and maintenance (DFO) methodologies. These three methodologies require a wide range of disciplines to work concurrently, as opposed to sequentially, during the concept design stage. In addition, technical and environmental challenges inhibiting the convergence of HKT designs require expertise from various scientific and engineering fields, necessitating the use of multi-disciplinary teams. These teams may include experts in hydrodynamics, mechanical design, materials, hydro-structural interactions, turbine and/or turbine array efficiency, system-level control solutions, power electronics, grid connection, numerical modeling, computer tools, and experimental validation. Projects will need to reduce the LCOE through multiple approaches, including increasing generation efficiency, increasing rotor area per unit of equivalent mass, lowering operation and maintenance costs, minimizing potential negative impacts on the surrounding environment, and maximizing system reliability among others.

³⁸ <https://www.nationalacademies.org/our-work/evaluation-of-the-advanced-research-projects-agency-energy-arpa-e>

The MARINER program provided funding starting in 2018 to develop several alternate means of growing macroalgae at sea in sufficient quantity to create feedstock for biofuels, with the intent of producing other value-added products along the way. In addition to funding a series of technical tools to assist with the growing and harvesting operations (e.g., numerical modeling for siting; autonomous vehicles for hauling product; sensors and autonomous underwater vehicles for determining water quality, light, and nutrient availability, and measuring growth; and selective breeding and genomics technologies), ARPA-E MARINER expects to move the successful growing and harvesting operations toward commercial viability.

Both of these examples highlight the diversity of projects that an ARPA-Ocean program could nurture and potentially integrate.

While the off-shore wind industry may now have sufficient size and commercial scale to invest in significant R&D, it is clear that the smaller-scale and more diverse set of ocean, tidal and other less-researched marine technologies would benefit greatly from such a suite of programs.

Figure 8 provides a real-world comparison of technology proposals that would greatly benefit from the ARPA-E model. While each candidate shown here – each actual technologies in either prototype or early product delivery phases – has promise, they are based on widely varying power generation premises, from fixed-mount drag systems, to flying wind, to bot-

tom-current to surface/wave extraction. This diversity would be quite challenging for single-winner technology only competitions. These distinct concepts, however, have so far proven to be very distinct from each other in both power output, and in potential synergies with the hardware for Hydrogen production as a complimentary application to electricity, to survivability based on ocean floor, mid-water column, or surface deployment as might be the case with algae, kelp, shellfish, or fin-fish production facilities. An ARPA-Ocean assessment team, however, would be well-suited to this sort of multi-dimensional assessment given the focus on multiple tiers of technological readiness.

Figure 8: technology comparison of diverse tidal and current generators all well-suited to an ARPA-Ocean comparative competition initiative.

	Developer	Model	Installed capacity	Rated capacity	Weight	Current velocity
	Minesto	DG500	Prototype testing	500 kW	30 tonnes	1.2-3.0 m/s
	SIMEC Atlantic Energy	AR1500	6 MW (4 units)	1,500 kW	150 tonnes	3.0-5.0 m/s
	Orbital Marine Power	Orbital O2	Prototype testing	2,000 kW	600 tonnes	2.5 m/s
	Nova Innovation	M100	0.3 MW (3 units)	100 kW	80 tonnes	2.0 m/s

These ‘TR’ levels (Table 4) have proven highly instructive in sorting technologies along very different metrics for promise and success (Majumdar, 2015).

In fact, we can be even more optimistic that the intensive attention that the ARPA-E model for ARPA-O is likely to be highly successful based on a recent assessment of four decades of US Department of Energy investment in wind power.

Table 4: ARPA-E Technological Readiness Levels.

TRL	
9	Actual technology system qualified through successful mission operations
8	Actual technology system completed and qualified through test and demonstration
7	Technology prototype demonstration in an operational environment
6	Technology demonstration in a relevant environment
5	Technology validation in relevant environment
4	Technology validation in laboratory
3	Analytical and experimental critical function and/or characteristic proof-of-concept
2	Technology concept and/or application formulated
1	Basic principles observed

In that study Wisner and Milstein (2019) considered public wind research expenditures and U.S. wind power deployment over the period 1976–2017, while also accounting for the full useful lifetime of wind projects built over this period. Assessed benefits include energy cost savings and health benefits due to reductions in air pollution. Overall, the analysis demonstrated sizable, positive economic returns on past wind energy research.

Under the core analysis and with a 3% real discount rate, the net benefits from historical federal wind energy research investments were found to equal \$31.4 billion, leading to an 18 to 1 benefit-to-cost ratio and an internal rate of return of 15.4%. Avoided car-

bon dioxide emissions were not valued in monetary terms, but are estimated at 1510 million metric tons, or \$75.5 billion using the social cost of carbon (we provide an example of additional health burdens that fall directly onto minority communities in Appendix 3). Alternative methods and input assumptions yield benefit-to-cost ratios that fall within a relatively narrow range from 7-to-1 to 21-to-1, reinforcing in broad terms the general finding of a sizable positive return on investment. Unsurprisingly, results are sensitive to the chosen discount rate, with higher discount rates leading to lower benefit-to-cost ratios, and lower discount rates yielding higher benefit-to-cost ratios.

Finally, we have not discussed OTEC or other ocean thermal energy systems extensively in this report, but recent promising studies in the Maldives and elsewhere highlight the potential of that technology as well³⁹. We will return to other thermal gradient systems, notably OTEC in the final section (7) of this assessment.

³⁹ <https://energy.economictimes.indiatimes.com/news/renewable/ocean-thermal-energy-ideal-to-power-maldives-study/70841340>

5. Scale-up marine Hydrogen Production for Zero-Carbon Transportation Sector

Many life-cycle assessments now find that the most economically competitive option for carbon free international travel, high-torque industrial demands, and for use in the chemical engineering sector, is Hydrogen.

The fuel of choice for cruise liners, ferries, and container ships will likely be hydrogen. Marine energy could supply the power to drive an electrolyzer, to produce hydrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide, and other potential gases. With the current technology, a freshwater source for electrolysis will be needed, but future technologies may be able to use seawater directly. Domestic and international chemical companies and transport organizations are likely partners for gases, such as hydrogen and ammonia, to power fuel cells or synthesize fuels at land-based operations.

With electrolyzers to produce industrial scale quantities of H₂ at the early stages of technological progress (and thus a prime ARPA-Ocean candidate), the potential for cost reductions is enormous. This places marine solar power, off-shore wind, and ocean thermal for H₂ production all as strong candidates to utilize

Figure 9: The proposed AquaVentus project that could see the product of 10 GW of green hydrogen electrolyzer capacity piped to shore by 2035⁴⁰.

marine energy at time of excess production relative to demand.

Japan, Europe and China all have developed plans for marine energy installations to serve as hubs for hydrogen production for pipeline or freighter transport to shore.

The European Union is now evaluating a plan to build 40 gigawatts of green hydrogen electrolyzers by 2030 and estimates that 80 to 120 gigawatts of solar and wind will be needed to power them.

Hydrogen Case Description 1

H₂ production at the European Marine Energy Center (EMEC) The European Marine Energy Center is producing hydrogen gas as a means to store unused renewable energy produced from tidal and wind energy (EMEC 2017). The hydrogen gas is being produced in the outer Orkney islands, off the northeast coast of Scotland, by 500- to 1,000-kilowatt (kW) solid oxide fuel cells— electrolyzer —that runs in regenerative mode to achieve electrolysis of fresh water and produce both hydrogen and oxygen. The hydrogen is transported to the main Orkney island for use in the intra-island ferry system and land transport. The hydrogen is compressed and transported to a fuel cell where it is converted back to electricity for local use. The electrolyzers used by EMEC to generate hydrogen and oxygen are 500- and 1,000-kW units, which can produce approximately 2,400 and 4,800 m³ of hydrogen per day (200 to 400 kg/d). There are units on the market that range from tens of kilowatts to 1,000-kW stand-alone units to multi unit systems that are greater than 10,000 kW. The typical energy needs of electrolyzer units are around 5 kilowatt-hours per m³ of hydrogen. Because the hydrogen is produced from a renewable energy source, it is a clean fuel, with no carbon emissions. EMEC is currently exploring a use for the oxygen that is also produced from this process. Applications of this type are most suitable for islands and island communities as well as remote locations where the cost of power is high and there are often remote areas requiring energy.

⁴⁰ <https://www.greentechmedia.com/articles/read/why-offshore-wind-and-energy-giants-are-chasing-off-grid-green-hyd>

Marine Energy – Hydrogen Production Hubs:

A range of proposals exist, and some are not going into commercial development, to make marine wind-farms also serve as Hydrogen (or Ammonia) production centers. The economic advantages are significant: when electricity prices either drop, or when total electricity generation outpaces demand, marine ‘energy hubs’ could switch over to Hydrogen production, which is then taken by ship or pipeline to shore. Figure 10 illustrates a number of these possible configurations, either for a fully marine based hub (10a), a shore-based production facility tied to marine energy by cable (10b), or from a floating electrolyzer platform with pipeline connectivity to the shore. Additional proposals now exist to do additional energy projects on site with ocean deployed collectors of power beamed from space solar platforms which can produce power continuously (save for a brief 50 minute window given a high-orbit geostationary location⁴¹). This makes further use of the resources and the water for Hydrogen production.

41 https://www.popularmechanics.com/science/energy/a35092898/air-force-solar-power-beaming-spacecraft/?utm_campaign=social-flowFBPOP&utm_medium=social-media&utm_source=facebook&fbclid=IwAR0uv17MMW1RwuB0lzlzM2sCDwlv0Hm4SISleFzz9fnOK-jy2EluFpKYGK4I

Seawater mining

Seawater contains large amounts of minerals, dissolved gases, and specific organic molecules that are more evenly distributed, albeit at lower concentrations, than in terrestrial locations. Lithium and uranium extraction are two of the more valuable materials under investigation.

Seawater contains large amounts of minerals, dissolved gases, and specific organic molecules. Some of the most valuable minerals include the 17 rare earth elements (REEs), precious metals, lithium, and uranium. Although land-based minerals are concentrated in specific geologic formations and geographic areas, seawater minerals are generally distributed evenly in seawater with some higher concentrations near continents as a result of terrestrial runoff and interaction with margin sediments. Minerals can be recovered from seawater using adsorption methods that do not require filtering vast amounts of seawater, while recovering other elements and compounds can require more energy-intensive processes.

Extracting minerals from seawater is a more environmentally friendly enterprise than terrestrial mining (Diallo et al. 2015; Congressional Research Service, 2017). Moreover, seawater extraction will not require fresh water for processing nor create volumes of contaminated water and tailings for disposal. Most REEs, as well as uranium and other minerals used in the United States, are imported from other nations, which raises supply chain concerns for both industry and national security. Dissolved gases like hydrogen can become important sources of energy storage and will be used in the future for maritime transportation. These critical materials are needed for many modern-day technologies, such as wind turbines, solar panels, and electric vehicles.

Figure 10: Floating solar --> H2 production

- Passive adsorption, and to a lesser extent electrochemical processes, are two different methods to extract elements and minerals directly from seawater. Several gases (e.g., CO₂, Hydrogen, and Oxygen) can be electrolytically produced directly from seawater. Most systems are in early stages of development, but a strong market demand exists for many of the end products.
- Power required for each method varies. Potential uses for power will be to assist in deploying and retrieving long adsorbent films, extracting elements via electrochemical mechanisms or electrolysis, pumping seawater, powering safety and monitoring equipment, as well as potentially powering the machinery or technology needed to remove elements from adsorbent material.
- Marine energy could open up unexploited opportunities in seawater mining, which could further expand mineral and gas markets. It is believed that linking a marine energy converter to a seawater mineral extraction technology could substantially enhance or enable the extraction process because of colocation benefits and greater power generation potential than other renewable technologies.

By linking a seawater extraction technology to a local power supply, such as tidal, wave, off-shore wind, or floating photovoltaics, a carbon-free extraction technology could be co-located at the marine energy hubs.

Electric Airplanes

The International Civil Aviation Organization estimates that by 2050, aircraft-generated emissions are going to triple in volume. Governments that recognize the dangers are responding to these skyrocketing greenhouse gases by increasing industry regulations. Starting in 2012, the European Union has implemented a carbon-trading program among airlines that creates a marketplace for trading or buying allowances for CO₂ emissions. In 2019, the International Air Transport Association adopted a resolution calling on more governments to follow the same path.

In the United States, aircraft emissions are largely un-

regulated, and industry leaders as well as politicians have long fought participation in international emission-reduction schemes. But big changes are around the corner. This year, the US Environmental Protection Agency announced it is going to study aircraft emissions to determine whether they are a risk to public health or the environment and potentially move to regulate them⁴². Reducing emissions could be as simple as improving flight path efficiency and fuel burn. These two factors alone would result in carbon-neutral growth in America, and save 1.4 billion gallons of fuel.

But incremental improvements may not be enough. The very concept of a fossil-fuel-powered airplane needs to evolve if impacts on the environment are going to be fully mitigated to prevent the worst effects of climate change.

Companies such as Safran S.A., Boeing, Airbus, and Raytheon have already revealed plans to re-conceptualize the modern airplane. At Boeing, engineers have created the SUGAR Volt concept plane which combines electricity and fuel to power flight, much like a hybrid automobile does. There is a lot at stake in the race to innovate: the electric aircraft market is projected to reach over \$22 billion in the next fifteen years (Figure 11). An additional example is the potential for sustainable fuel production at remote locations like Hawai'i (Appendix 4).

In order for electric flight to really take off and become mainstream in both commercial and recreational markets, it needs better batteries. Other industries have replaced traditional lead-acid batteries with lithium-ion batteries, which now power most of our laptops, phones, and electric cars. But in order to be aviation compatible, the next generation of batteries needs to deliver a very large amount of power while being simultaneously smaller, safer, and lighter than lithium-ion ones.

Planes like the Taurus G4, made by Slovenian airplane manufacturer Pipistrel, have already proved that electric planes are not just green and cheap but can also perform better: Taurus needs less runway to take off and climbs faster than the same model that relies on

⁴² <https://www.theatlantic.com/sponsored/thomson-reuters-why-2025-matters/electric-flight/208/>

fuel. And because electric planes are nearly silent, they have the potential to be flown and landed near dwellings and businesses. These facts mean that in a couple generations, teenagers could be getting a pilot’s license rather than a driver’s license and landing their small aircraft in a high school parking lot.

The world has already come a long way toward creating an era of environmentally smarter, battery-powered flight. Klaus Ohlmann’s flight in the e-Genius was five times as long as the first electric flight in 1973. “E-mobility,” said Ohlmann, “starts now.”

Figure 11: A range of electric aircraft models are under development or testing. First movement into the mainstream large-passenger volume and long-distance market may be accomplished by programs like E-Fan X⁴³. Airbus too, has a decade transition plan, where, as with solar, early markets and R&D on the light-duty market will be utilized to accomplish growth through rapid learning, and then evolving into the long-haul market⁴⁴.

43 The E-Fan platform intended to swap one engine out in favor of a 2 MW battery-powered electric motor to test, successively, more and more engine systems replacing jet engines.

44 <https://www.airbus.com/innovation/zero-emission/electric-flight.html>

6. Prioritize Research and Partnerships to Expand of Pilot Programs that Build the Zero-Carbon Marine Energy-Food Nexus

The United Nations forecasts that we will need to produce 50% more food by 2050 to feed another 2.5 billion people (FAO, 2018). Present agricultural practices cannot scale to meet this demand without a major modification in the way agriculture is implemented. Further, there are not enough freshwater or land resources to accomplish this sustainably, and environmental burdens including greenhouse gas emissions, runoff, and soil degradation will only increase, as will levels of impact on natural lands and on marginalized human populations (Willett et al., 2019). The production of these animal protein sources takes a large environmental toll. Raising livestock requires a significant amount of freshwater and land both to support animals directly and to produce the agricultural crops they require as feed. Livestock production also accounts for between 14.5% and 18% of human-induced greenhouse gas emissions (Searchinger et al., 2018). Most of these emissions are directly emitted by cattle and other ruminants, like sheep and buffalo, which use bacteria in their stomachs to ferment food.

Today, the ocean produces about 17% of global per capita consumption of animal protein (FAO, 2018). These resources are particularly important for many of the world's poorest citizens. Protein from seafood is a significant source of high-quality nutrients and is essential in the diets of some densely populated countries. The ocean's contribution to the total global food supply, however, is far smaller. While covering 71% of Earth's surface, the world ocean contributes only about 2% to the world's food supply on a caloric basis (FAO, 2018).

Some countries, including the United States, have established environmentally and economically responsible management of wild-capture fisheries in their territorial seas. Well-managed fisheries play an important role in providing nutritious food to the growing and increasingly affluent population. As is the subject of the Marine Food working group report, and as is the subject of numerous reports, more than 90% of glob-

al fish stocks are fished at or above sustainable limits. With appropriate science-based management that includes setting aside more and larger areas of the ocean for protection, most experts find that while some expansion of wild-capture harvests is possible, this expansion will be modest (Bennett, et al, 2018; Lester et al., 2009, 2018a, b).

A number of recent assessments have explored both the risks and the potential for greatly increased marine protein and plant production for human consumption (c.f. Lester, et al., 2018b, Packard Foundation, 2018).

But scaling-up when explored in isolation to other marine opportunities poses a number of challenges. Offshore operations are more expensive than current terrestrial agriculture, and may well be higher in cost than nearshore and land-based aquaculture production. Of course, a large part of that equation is based on agricultural and livestock practices that are historically heavily subsidized (both directly and indirectly) and thus unlikely to yield easily to new environmental-economic metrics such as carbon pricing, or the social cost of carbon, even when efforts are launched at the federal level (NAS, 2017).

Achieving economies of scale for marine food production will be critical for successful offshore marine aquaculture businesses. Siting and operating farms offshore also requires significant investment. Today it can be difficult to secure investments when the process to permit these operations is so unpredictable. Securing permits in state and federal waters is difficult and time consuming. As explored by Schubel and Thompson (2019), with few exceptions, permitting marine aquaculture requires a lot of time and money that can discourage investments and growth in the sector. In many cases, permitting in federal waters, this is because the regulatory framework is complex and lacks leadership. Even beyond the regulatory issues, challenges that are associated with negative public perceptions, typically driven by small but politically influential special interest groups that can stop projects at an early stage.

These issues are all very similar to those faced by off-shore energy production. This not only suggests strongly that lessons learned from marine energy can aid in developing meaningful, inclusive and transpar-

ent environmental (and cultural) impact assessments for food – and the converse – but that an even greater synergy exists for the co-development, co-location, and community dialog process that can and should link marine energy and marine food development.

This statement of the synergies in barriers to marine energy and food, while obvious in many ways to experts in each field has not been pursued as an operational strategy for sustainable and equitable evaluation, development, and operation of marine energy-food systems. This nexus is a potential huge advance in both fields.

While there is no simple means to correct this impasse, the advances in marine energy and food need to be brought more clearly into alignment. We have explored several opportunities to greatly expand these synergies.

As an example of technology that permits an ‘upward tipping point’, consider the Salt Water Air Conditioning (SWAC) technology for air conditioning (Figure 12). SWAC is a nearly passive system of a deep suction pipe where the water is cold (in the case of this site in Bora Bora, roughly 5.5 degrees C). The cold water is pulled up without energy input roughly a kilometer with negative pressure. The cold water drives a heat

exchanger and then cooled surface water is used to air condition the buildings. The still cold water can also be diverted to agricultural fields, where it is then possible to grow temperate zone crops. The warmed water is then returned at a shallower depth (in this case, at 13 degrees C).

Piloting Food-Energy Nexus Projects

Co-location of marine energy and food production to take advantage of infrastructure, permitting, and logistics offers significant benefits to both sectors.

In an important recent study Costello and colleagues (2020) find that under-estimated demand shifts and supply scenarios (which account for policy reform and technology improvements), edible food from the sea could increase by 21 – 44 million tonnes by 2050, which is a 36 – 74% increase compared to current yields. This represents 12–25% of the estimated increase in all meat needed to feed 9.8 billion people by 2050. Increases in three protein sectors (marine wild fisheries, finfish mariculture, and bivalve mariculture) are likely, but are most pronounced for mariculture. Whether these production potentials are realized sustainably will depend on factors such as policy reforms, technological innovation and the extent of future shifts in demand. These results are summarized in Figure 13.

Figure 12: Salt Water Air Conditioning (SWAC) in operation.

We note that this impressive study neither explores the combined food potential of fish/bivalve protein and plant-based foods, nor does it examine how to leverage off-shore zero carbon energy infrastructure.

At minimum a study could be undertaken to evaluate off-shore energy production to account for at least 25% of total energy demands and up to 100% of total food needs.

The Co-benefits of Social Justice in Marine Energy and Food

The largest un-studied synergy in marine energy-food systems, is likely not to be technical, economic or ecological. By featuring community participation through planning, siting, addressing the needs of marginalized and under-served coastal communities, it is very possible that far faster and more sustainable growth in both marine food and energy production is possible. While there is a great deal of negative experience with industrial-scale marine overfishing and destructive coastal food development (e.g. shrimp-farming in southeast Asia, Chanratchakool and Phillips, 2001; Gatsiounis,

2008), little has been done to make community participation, oversight, and profits a core development objective that utilizes metrics such as the social cost of carbon, local sustainable employment in both the energy and food sectors.

Carbon Negative Food Systems

Research teams are instead interested in the methane-inhibiting properties of an unlikely source: the seaweed. *Asparagopsis*⁴⁵, a warm-water seaweed species grown in Australia, contains a compound called bromoform that when used to comprise as little as 2% of a cow’s diet, reduces the animal’s methane emissions by up to 98%. There are, however, questions over whether cows like the taste of bromoform – in some experiments livestock reduced the amount they ate after the seaweed was introduced to their diet. Bromoform can be carcinogenic in humans, although there is little research to show whether this is transferred into any meat and dairy products. Many people are also already exposed to low levels of bromoform through tap water.

Figure 13: a–c, Supply and demand curves for marine wild fisheries (a), finfish mariculture (b) and bivalve mariculture (c). In each panel, the solid black line is the supply curve from Fig. 3: for wild fisheries, the rational reform scenario is shown, and for finfish mariculture the technological innovation (ambitious) scenario is shown. Future demand refers to estimated demand in 2050; extreme demand represents a doubling of the estimated demand in 2050. The intersections of demand and sustainable supply curve (indicated with crosses) provide an estimate of the future food from the sea. Points represent current production and average price in each sector. From Costello, et al., 2020.

45 <https://www.bbc.com/future/bespoke/follow-the-food/the-foods-that-reverse-climate-change/>

Appendix 1

Na Pua Makani - An Ongoing Lesson in Community and Ecological Conflict - Off-shore energy conflicts, justifiable NIMBY-ism and environmental racism

Switching to greater reliance on renewable energy can diversify sources of energy, reduce carbon dioxide emissions, reduce air pollution and meet growing demands for electricity. As renewable energy infrastructure scales up, it is becoming increasingly common in and near where people live. Siting this infrastructure has often been controversial, resulting in project delays and cancellations. A number of scholars and community activists have identified a ‘social gap’ when it comes to understanding why national opinion polls reveal high levels of public support for the development of renewable energy while specific applications for its development have low success rates. Proposed explanations for this ‘social gap’ include the following nomenclature:

1. **self-interested NIMBY-ism** (not in my backyard), defined as “an attitude motivated by concern for the ‘common good’ and behavior motivated by ‘self-interest’”
2. **democratic deficit** in that a small, unrepresentative number of opponents dominate the decision processes;
3. **qualified support** in that national surveys may report high levels of public support, but this support may in reality be based on certain conditions being met (e.g., related to noise, size, number of turbines, environmental protection, community engagement, fairness of decision process, and fair allocation of economic benefits); and
4. **place protectors**, who perceive higher place value in a specific location without the renewable energy development (e.g., rejecting a development due to its impact on local biodiversity or the historic qualities of a particular landscape), but may accept the development in another location.

If renewable energy targets are to be achieved, this “social gap” must be bridged to mitigate, accommodate or otherwise work through concerns of local communities to particular renewable energy projects.

Social science can elucidate why and how renewable energy controversies might be ameliorated via robust public engagement strategies, including those that seek to clarify both concerns and possible outcomes or alternatives. Public participation in decision-making has the potential to enhance the quality of decision outcomes while improving the capacity of those involved to meaningfully engage in policy processes. Scholars of risk, technology and social dimensions of renewable energy recommend shifting governance away from reliance on primarily technocratic evaluations of risks and benefits. Instead, scholars have called for methods that ‘open-up’ the capacity for people with diverse perspectives to participate in analytic deliberative processes to determine what constitutes appropriate development of a technology. Analytic-deliberative methods are approaches to public engagement in decision-making that involve assessment and dialogue to reconcile technical as well as expert knowledge with citizen values. Such methods can result in increased trust among those involved and acceptability of outcomes. “Opening up” decision-making processes entails recognition and accounting for the numerous factors driving the development and deployment of technology, including “individual creativity, collective ingenuity, economic priorities, cultural values, institutional interests, stakeholder negotiation, and the exercise of power”. And yet, when done poorly (i.e., closing down decision making), deliberative processes can ‘close’ down both discussion of new technologies and so too the possibility of innovations (e.g., offshore wind farms) and potential paradigm shifts (e.g., a move from large corporate-owned to distributed community-owned energy systems).

The battles over development projects without local voice are not new, of course. An ongoing case in Hawaii illustrates both the battles over implementation without consultation, hence illegitimate outcomes in the language, but also the ways in which emerging technology – in this case off-shore wind, may open new pro-energy and pro-community outcomes.

Na Pua Makani: An Ongoing Lesson in Community and Ecological Conflict

Located on the northeast tip of O‘ahu Hawai‘i, the rural village of Kahuku sits directly exposed to the Pacific trade winds. The near year-round persistence of these winds make the hills above town an ideal location for a wind farm. A site, judged by corporate meteorologists, that is the best on the entire island.

With a population of only 2,097 people, the residents of Kahuku are no strangers to wind farms. Beginning in the early 1980’s, Hawaiian Electric Industries (HEI) invested over \$32 million to develop a 9 MW wind farm at Kahuku, anchored by what was then the world’s largest horizontal axis wind turbine, rated at 3.2 MW. However, winds were more turbulent than expected and the first-generation turbines ran into mechanical problems. In addition, a dramatic drop in the price of oil made the wind farm too costly to operate. It was later sold to New World Power and has since been closed and the turbines dismantled.

In 2011 the Kahuku Wind Farm was officially commissioned. Consisting of 12, 2.5 MW turbines and a 15 MW energy storage battery to ensure power during slack periods, the project had a generating capacity of 30 MW, enough to power 7,700 homes. However, in 2012 the energy storage building caught fire and burned for three days sending toxic fumes spewing into the air. It took over 15 months for the project to recover, during which time it operated at less than 20% capacity.

With winds troubled history, and a total of 42 towering turbines spread across O‘ahu’s North Shore, residents voiced increasing concern with plans to further expand wind power in the area. In response, Boston-based First Wind, Inc. announced in 2012 that it was scrapping plans to add 5 additional turbines to its Kahuku farm. So when news broke in late 2013 that a new developer was moving forward with plans for 15 more turbines in Kahuku, it was taken poorly by residents and came across as particularly tone-deaf.

In truth, the first public meetings about the Na Pua Makani project were poorly attended and support was offered by non-resident groups like Sierra Club and the Surfrider Foundation. But concerns were expressed about the placement of turbines too close to Kahuku High School and some residences, and references to the battery building fire, and the fact that Kahuku was generating electricity for the whole island and seeing little local benefit, came up repeatedly. In response to these comments, the project was scaled down from 15 to 8 turbines, but their location close to the community was not resolved.

After nearly four decades of wind projects that were concocted by corporate interests located in some off-shore office, the residents of Kahuku were tired of reacting to what other people thought were good ideas. The fundamental lack of community-based planning was wearing thin on the families of the rural community. It was always one developer after another, coming to town with their ideas of what the community should be willing to tolerate. The impatience and frustration

Figure A: a (left): Schematic of Kahuku wind-farm proposed full-build-out plan and noise-level zones; b (right) Eight turbines in the Na Pua Makani wind farm in Kahuku while under construction (Ab: Chip Fletcher).

of residents finally boiled over in October 2019 when peaceful protesters blocked a convoy of trucks scheduled to deliver turbine components to construction sites in the hills above Kahuku. A total of 55 peaceful protesters were arrested, 22 at the staging yard where the truck convoy was attempting to depart, and 33 at Kahuku.

The protests continued for weeks, but eventually all equipment was delivered to construction sites and the turbines have now been built and are generating power. The moral of this story is that developers should engage in community-based planning that springs from a true partnership that works to find the right mix of ownership by those families most affected by the project, and a project that pencils out for a developer who has to balance many needs among which is the need to make a profit.

As Hawaii makes generally impressive steps toward their 100% clean energy target, an important and cautionary test case has emerged on Oahu that has garnered international attention⁴⁶. The local opposition group “No Napua” has compiled a detailed set of critiques of the project⁴⁷, and has engaged in peaceful protest to the ongoing construction.

Chief Operating Officer for the AES US Generation businesses, the company running Na Pua Makani, Mark Miller issued a statement:

“After years of studies, securing all necessary approvals and completing construction of our turbines, later this year Na Pua Makani will start delivering enough energy to power up to 16,000 homes on O’ahu. We look forward to working with elected officials and the State of Hawai’i to achieve its renewable energy future.”

However, Hawaii State Senator Gil Riviere (D) made a statement that there is now a renewed political and legal charge to challenge the wind farm:

“There’s three very real legal challenges that are pending on this case,” Senator Riviere stated.

Keep the North Shore Country, a nonprofit with which Senator Riviere is involved appealed to the City & County of Honolulu’s Department of Planning and Permitting regarding the Land Use Ordinance for the wind farm was granted a hearing on March 5, 2020.

“If they can’t sell electricity or their [sic] are not allowed to operate because they’re killing endangered species or if they have to tear down turbines because they’re in the setback I think that’s going to hurt their ability to operate,” he added.

Kahuku community member Jessica Dos Santos said the following in a statement:

“Our community has been continuing to fight and we now find ourselves joining with other communities to advocate for environmental justice in the state. The Kahuku community still has the same concerns and demands as they’ve always had with this project.

We are supporting our elected officials who have introduced a package of bills to address the issues which our fight in Kahuku has exposed, in order to move our state towards a more just, safe and equitable transition to clean energy. We hope others in the state will talk to their elected officials to support us as well.

We are especially hopeful that lawmakers will support the proposition that would allow the governor to negotiate the termination of the project to protect the safety and health of our community and to right the wrongs that have been committed in this 10 year fight, as well as others that include setback minimums and longitudinal health studies in affected communities.

There are three unresolved legal issues which we hope will affect the industrial turbine project’s ability to operate in Kahuku. The challenge to the inadequate habitat conservation plan that does not meet the requirements of the endangered species act is in the intermediate court of appeals,

⁴⁶ Lemieux, Melissa (2019) “Hawaiian wind farm protesters arrested, say windmills too close to homes, citing noise pollution and migraines”, Newsweek, <https://www.newsweek.com/hawaiian-wind-farm-protesters-arrested-say-windmills-too-close-homes-citing-noise-pollution-1466377>

⁴⁷ <https://nonapua.com>

the Life of the Land's Motion for Relief, which seeks to invalidate the power purchase agreement between HECO and the Na Pua Makani wind project as it did not meet the legal requirements in that process and most recently the Keep the North Shore Country petition with the Honolulu Zoning Board of Appeals, as they wrongfully permitted Na Pua Makani turbines to be located closer to homes and schools than legally allowed under the Land Use Ordinance. The community will be at that contested case hearing on March 5th."

Legal History of the Na Pua Makani Dispute

HONOLULU – This week, Senator Gil Riviere introduced the POWER Bill Package – People Overwhelmed by Wind Energy Ramifications.

The gigantic wind turbines being built in Kahuku by Na Pua Makani surround the small rural community with industrial machinery towering as high as 57 stories and as close as 1650 feet from homes and schools. "The rally cry, 'Too big, too close' is no exaggeration," says the Senator.

The residents of Kahuku have lived within ¾ of a mile of 420' turbines since Kahuku Wind began operations in 2011. During the first year, that project experienced three fires from its battery system; the final, catastrophic fire spewed toxic gases for days and knocked the system off the grid for more than a year.

Kahuku residents are concerned about health and safety risks associated with living so close to these new, massive turbines. They are concerned about tower collapse and blade throw that has occurred at other projects, including Auwahi Wind on Maui. They are concerned about health risks and annoyance from infrasound, low frequency sound, incessant whoosh and grinding noises of the turbines, stray voltage, nighttime flashing lights, and shadow flicker.

The POWER Bill Package includes measures targeting the need for health studies and discounted electricity rates for residents burdened by living near the turbines, reasonable setbacks, and a siting process for renewable energy. The siting process will be critical to help prevent similar crises from happening again.

"I also introduced a measure calling on Governor Ige to begin negotiations with Na Pua Makani to terminate this poorly located project. Something this big and this close to residents should never have been approved.

"This divisive project threatens the health and well-being of the people of Kahuku and could harm the implementation of future renewable energy projects the State is relying on to meet its clean energy

initiative. The Governor is in the best position to help reverse this terrible mistake."

The Na Pua Makani turbines are a third taller and more than twice as close to residents as the original project, Kahuku Wind. Together, these two industrial wind projects will surround the residents, whose objections to the project have been ignored for years.

Senator Riviere introduced the POWER Bill package to offer a suite of solutions:

SB 2801 - requires the Public Utilities Commission to establish preferential electricity rates for residential properties located within a five-mile radius of a utility scale wind energy facility.

SB 2802 - requires all wind turbines that are equipped with obstruction lighting and located within five miles of a residential community to be equipped with aircraft detection lighting systems and turn off lights when there are no aircrafts in the area to reduce light pollution.

SB 2803 - requires all utility scale wind energy facilities operating within two miles of a residential area to provide a longitudinal monitoring study of residents living within two miles of the facility.

SB 2804 - requires each county to adopt ordinances that require wind turbines and other wind-powered energy systems to be setback at least fifteen feet for each foot of height.

SB 3048 - Prohibits utility-scale energy projects from being constructed or located within half a mile from the boundary of any residential area.

SB 2805 - requires the Office of Planning to prepare a comprehensive renewable energy siting plan.

SB 3051 - authorizes the Governor, or the Governor's designee, to terminate the Na Pua Makani wind energy project.

As of September, 2020, the measures in the POWER Bill Package have not yet been scheduled for public hearing.

Sunset Beach Community Association

P.O. Box 471
Haleiwa, HI. 96712

October 8, 2019

SBCA 1959-2019

Dear Mayor Caldwell,

Please rescind the Na Pua Makani Wind Farm building permit to protect public health from audible and low-frequency noise. We believe Na Pua Makani Wind Farm underrepresented the level of audible sound the wind farm would produce, and failed to disclose the significant public health risks associated with wind turbine noise pollution. September 10, 2019, AES told Laie Community Association attendees the wind farm's audible sound would exceed the levels previously disclosed to the public, which warrants your removal of the building permit (https://vimeo.com/359776610?fbclid=IwAR0HJ48uqZc5p2am1eA2jC7bxJIC-b11ZI9NE_jYAoVYH-jHb1qcDT2HDJ4).

The existing Kawaihoa and Kahuku Wind Farms adversely affect resident sleep and health; residents find relief when the wind stops blowing and the turbines are not operating. To inform DPP's development of updated wind turbine setback requirements, please establish a secure portal for residents to submit private information about the effects existing wind turbines are having to their health. We are concerned the proposed wind turbines would dramatically affect human health in Kahuku. In addition, because the proposed turbines would be larger and cause higher decibel levels of low-frequency impulse sound than smaller existing turbines, we are concerned the proposed very large turbines could cause sleep disturbance in Beach, Haleiwa, and Waiialua neighborhoods. If Na Pua Makani continues to pursue a permit to construct the project, please ensure the applicant discloses the maximum sound pressure level of 0 to 1.5 Hz impulse sound Na Pua Makani Wind Farm would cause on the landscape.

Sincerely,

for Andrea Woods
Corresponding Secretary

Figure C: Local television reporting on protesters signs at the wind-farm site, which will include the largest on-land turbines in the United States.

Figure D: Community gathering to protest wind farms.

Appendix 2

Vineyard Community Power: A different approach to community engagement

Vineyard Power grew out of Martha's Vineyard's Island Plan, a sustainability strategy that the Martha's Vineyard Commission completed based on input from thousands of island residents in 2009 to "create the future we want rather than settle for the future we get.". This plan included a recommendation to create a community-owned renewable energy cooperative so islanders could have more autonomy over their energy production and better ensure community benefits associated with renewable energy development. In 2009, Vineyard Power began recruiting members. People joined for social reasons (e.g., inclusion in the decision making processes in an island-owned, action-oriented group to create a more sustainable energy future for their community) and financial rewards (e.g., ownership and control of local renewable energy projects and stabilized electricity prices once a large-scale renewable energy project is developed). The co-

operative's community benefits are embedded in the cooperative's mission: "to produce electricity from local, renewable resources while advocating for and keeping the benefits within our island community"⁴⁸.

Vineyard Power staff explained how they learned from the controversy over the nearby Cape Wind project and consequently worked to integrate benefits, including partial ownership, to island residents. The cooperative also engaged community members in the wind farm decision process. It hired a consultant who used the industry standard windPRO tool to generate interactive visualizations and administer a visual impact survey in 2010. The survey of co-op members and island residents found that island to turbine distances of 6–7 miles were acceptable to a majority. Staff at the energy cooperative described how the wind map viewer provided accessible information about visual, ecological and human use impacts based on various proposed sites, including data collected from local sources such as island fishermen. The cooperative also hosted a series of community meetings to share wind farm visualizations and solicit feedback⁴⁹.

48 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214629617301172#bib0260>

49 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214629617301172#bib0265>

In January 2015, BOEM auctioned the rights to lease offshore wind in areas in federal waters south of Martha's Vineyard. The wind farm developer, Offshore MW, received a 10% discount on their bid price because they had executed a Community Benefit Agreement (CBA) with Vineyard Power. The CBA outlined opportunities to investigate local benefits to the island including job creation, an operations and maintenance facility, and local equity ownership in the project⁵⁰.

The country is on track to go from just one operational wind farm—a 30-megawatt project with five turbines off Rhode Island—to a host of projects along the East Coast. Several states have set targets for offshore wind energy development, led by New York, which is aiming for 9,000 megawatts by 2035, and their ability to meet their clean energy goals depends on these projects.

Some of the recently announced projects would be larger than Vineyard Wind, including a 1.1 gigawatt wind farm that has won a state contract in New Jersey, but Vineyard Wind has a head start⁵¹.

50 <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214629617301172#bib0270>

51 McKenna, P and Gearino D (2019) "Government Delays First Big U.S. Offshore Wind Farm. Is a Double Standard at Play?" <https://insideclimatenews.org/news/19082019/vineyard-wind-offshore-renewable-energy-delay-boem-environmental-cumulative-review-nepa-massachusetts>

Appendix 3

Marine Energy Harnessed for the Health Impacts of Retiring Peaker Plants

Gas-fired power plant emissions create air pollution that causes serious adverse local and regional health effects⁵². Health impacts of natural gas power plants can happen hundreds of miles away from the source, and numerous studies have linked proximity near power plants with negative health effects, including adverse birth outcomes, like preterm births, hospital visits for respiratory illness, acute coronary issues, reduced lung function in children, and increased emergency room visits among the elderly⁵³. The air and water pollution emitted by coal and natural gas plants is also linked to respiratory problems, neurological damage, heart attacks, cancer, premature death, and a host of other serious problems⁵⁴. Most of these negative health impacts come from air and water pollution that wind energy technologies simply do not produce⁵⁵.

In addition to the many life-altering health impacts caused by peaker plants and CCGT emissions, environmental justice communities are now further at risk

with the COVID-19 pandemic. In April 2020, a nationwide study from Harvard University identified a clear link between long-term exposure to PM_{2.5} and NO₂ pollution and COVID-19 mortality rates⁵⁶. The COVID-19 health crisis has further highlighted the inequitable burden of health disparities these communities face. As of 2019, there were 195 peaker and CCGT plants in California, providing approximately 32 GW of generation capacity to the grid⁵⁷. 152 of the 195 plants are located within 5 miles of the top 25th percentile of CalEnviroScreen 3.0 census tracts⁵⁸. This means that 78% of these power plants are located in communities identified as the most disadvantaged, whereas only 9% of power plants are located in the bottom 25th percentile of CalEnviroScreen 3.0, or near communities that are the least disadvantaged⁵⁹. The disproportionate number of peaker plants in environmental justice communities compared to the sparse placement of peaker plants in non-disadvantaged communities is a clear indication of environmental injustice. With neighboring CCGTs and peaker plants, these environmental justice communities will be exposed to much worse air quality and have an increased risk of illness, long-term health issues, and other potential disasters caused by gas power plants⁶⁰. Environmental justice communities

52 J. A. De Gouw, D. Parrish, G. Frost, M. Trainer. Reduced emissions of CO₂, NO_x, and SO₂ from US power plants owing to switch from coal to natural gas with combined cycle technology. *Earth's Future*, 2 (2) (2014), pp. 75-82. <https://www.scopus.com/record/display.uri?eid=2-s2.0-84906540227&origin=inward&txGid=89045a57fee3fd7861f3ffe136d596b2>

53 Living in a zip code containing a fossil fuel-fired power plant increases your estimated rate of hospitalization 11% for asthma, 15% for acute respiratory infection, and 17% for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease among individuals older than the age of ten. See: X. Liu, L. Lessner, D.O. Carpenter. Association between residential proximity to fuel-fired power plants and hospitalization rate for respiratory diseases. *Environ. Health Perspect.*, 120 (6) (2012), p. 807. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1104146>

Elena M. Krieger, and Joan A. Casey, and Seth B.C. Shonkoff. A framework for siting and dispatch of emerging energy resources to realize environmental and health benefits: Case study on peaker power plant displacement. *Energy Policy*. Volume 96, September 2016, Pages 302-313 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2016.05.049>.

Avol EL, Gauderman WJ, Tan SM, London SJ, Peters JM. Respiratory effects of relocating to areas of differing air pollution levels. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2001; 164:2067-2072.

54 J.I. Levy, S.L. Greco, J.D. Spengle. The importance of population susceptibility for air pollution risk assessment: a case study of power plants near Washington D.C. *Environ. Health Perspect.*, 110 (12) (2002), p. 1253

55 Ibid.

56 Air pollution linked with higher COVID-19 death rates. Harvard T.H. Chan School of Public Health. May 5, 2020. <https://www.hsph.harvard.edu/news/hsph-in-the-news/air-pollution-linked-with-higher-covid-19-death-rates/>

57 From Brightline's analysis based on data from CEC 2019 Annual Generation- Plant Unit report. https://ww2.energy.ca.gov/almanac/electricity_data/web_qfer/Annual_Generation-Plant_Unit_cms.php

58 Based on Brightline's GIS analysis of publicly available data sourced from California Energy Commission (CEC) 2019 Power Plant Generator Data (via ArcGIS Online) and 2019 CalEnviroScreen 3.0 data (via ArcGIS Online). CalEnviroScreen mapping tool incorporates cumulative environmental burden and socioeconomic data.

59 The CPUC considered "disadvantaged communities" those that are in the top 25th percentile of the CalEnviroScreen 3.0 (OEHHA 2017).

Based on Brightline's GIS analysis of publicly available data sourced from California Energy Commission (CEC) 2019 power plant generator data (via ArcGIS Online) and 2019 CalEnviroScreen 3.0 data (via ArcGIS Online).

60 Elena M. Krieger. Natural gas power plants in California's disadvantaged communities. PSE Healthy Energy. April 2017 https://www.psehealthyenergy.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/CA.EJ_Gas_Plants.pdf

experience the most cumulative environmental health burdens, and when exposed to environmental health stressors, especially poor air quality, they are more likely to experience adverse health outcomes⁶¹. Reducing fossil fuel emissions is the only action to cease the further infliction of these detrimental health impacts on front-line communities.

Offshore Wind Can Help Phase Out Demand for Peaker Plants.

To successfully phase out peaker plants, offshore wind and other renewable energy sources will need to be paired with energy storage technologies that are crucial for providing deployable round-the-clock electricity. Models applied by the Union of Concerned Scientists found that in 2018, 23% of CCGT generation capacity and 24% of peaker capacity could be retired within the same year without negatively affecting grid reliability⁶². The removal of even one peaker plant results in substantial air pollution reduction.

Figure Ca: Maps of natural gas power plants and impacted communities⁶³.

61 R. Morello-Frosch, M. Pastor, J. Sadd. Environmental justice and Southern California’s “riskscape” the distribution of air toxics exposures and health risks among diverse communities Urban Aff. Rev., 36 (4) (2001), pp. 551-578.
 L. Cushing, J. Faust, L.M. August, R. Cendak, W. Wieland, G. Alexeeff. Racial/ethnic disparities in cumulative environmental health impacts in California: evidence from a statewide environmental justice screening tool (CalEnviroScreen 1.1) Am. J. Public Health, 0 (2015), pp. e1-e8.

Bell, M.L., Zanobetti, A., Dominici, F., Who is more affected by ozone pollution? A systematic review and meta-analysis. Am. J. Epidemiol., J.I. Levy, S.L. Greco, J.D. Spengle. The importance of population susceptibility for air pollution risk assessment: a case study of power plants near Washington D.C. Environ. Health Perspect., 110 (12) (2002), p. 1253.

62 Turning Down the Gas in California: The Role of Natural Gas in the State’s Clean Electricity. Union of Concerned Scientists <https://www.ucsusa.org/sites/default/files/attach/2018/07/Turning-Down-Natural-Gas-California-fact-sheet.pdf>

63 Based on Brightline’s GIS analysis of publicly available data sourced from California Energy Commission (CEC) 2019 power plant generator data (via ArcGIS Online) and 2019 CalEnviroScreen 3.0 data (via ArcGIS Online). CalEnviroScreen mapping tool incorporates cumulative environmental burden and socioeconomic data.

Peakers can economically be an ideal entry point for offshore wind and battery storage, although peaker plants are cheap to build, they are costly to run—more expensive than larger “baseload” gas, coal, nuclear, and hydroelectric plants⁶⁴. If battery prices come down, even modestly, about 82% of new peaker capacity could instead be replaced by batteries charged with renewables⁶⁵. Reducing California’s dependence on gas-fired power plants would result in significant health and economic benefits in environmental justice communities for generations⁶⁶.

Figure Cb: Offset calculations have been produced with peaker emissions data of 8,541,797 metric tons of CO₂ (from filtered EIA 2018 data: <https://www.eia.gov/electricity/data/emissions/>) and converted with EPA Greenhouse Gas Equivalencies Calculator (<https://www.epa.gov/energy/greenhouse-gas-equivalencies-calculator>). Passenger vehicles are defined as 2-axle 4-tire vehicles, including passenger cars, vans, pickup trucks, and sport/utility vehicles with an average fuel economy of 22.3 miles per gallon traveling 11,484 miles per year.

⁶⁴ Alan Neuhauser. Where Batteries Are Replacing Power Plants. US News. May 21, 2019 <https://www.usnews.com/news/national-news/articles/2019-05-21/why-california-nixed-a-natural-gas-power-plant-in-favor-of-batteries>

⁶⁵ Ibid.

⁶⁶ Benefits of Renewable Energy Use. Union of Concerned Scientists. Jul 14, 2008. https://www.unicef-irc.org/publications/pdf/ccc_final_2014.pdf (last updated Dec 20, 2017).

Carbon Dependent Today

In the century since Twain's travel in Hawai'i, this remote archipelago has come to symbolize the modern world's dependency on high-carbon for air travel. Residents are reliant on commercial airliners to move from island to island, or to visit loved ones out of state. And the largest civilian industry, tourism, generated at its pre-COVID-19 height as many as ten million passengers per year (see Figure D1).

Because of this reliance on jet travel, the greenhouse gas impact of Hawai'i's aviation emissions are more than ten times the global average, at 25.1%. Several startups have initiated research and development on hybrid-electric and battery powered small aircraft that can accommodate a handful of passengers over short trips. These craft may replace conventional jets for short-range flights, but a replacement for long-haul flights is decades away.

Annually, 22 billion gallons of jet fuel is produced in the US, a significant part of the 80 billion gallons produced around the world. The airline industry and the Federal Aviation Administration have been investigating alternative fuels in an effort to cut reliance on fossil fuels, improve fuel security, reduce pollution and address climate change concerns

Decarbonizing Aviation

Hawai'i, and island states more generally, require leadership on climate change, and are driven by necessity to expedite efforts to decarbonize aviation. Our economies are dependent on aviation and imported fuels. We have abundant solar and wind resources, and the raw feedstocks required to manufacture synthetic kerosene.

The industrial model outlined in this article would allow island states to become essentially fuel-independent, subject only to the financing model for the construction of the plants. And fundamentally, climate change is an existential threat for our homes – so it's in our economic and social interest to make this work. And it is in the broad interest of the climate community that Direct Air Capture becomes commercially viable.

The aviation industry has echoed the scientific community's calls for carbon neutrality. In 2009, the International Air Transport Association (IATA) presented the aviation industry's environmental goal, a net reduction in carbon emissions of 50% by 2050 compared to 2005. And in 2012 the Air Transport Action Group (ATAG) published non-binding targets for the aviation industry, including a cap of the fleet's net CO₂ emissions through carbon-neutral growth from 2020. ATAG also reiterated halving the fleet's annual net CO₂ emissions by 2050 relative to the level of 2005.

Avoiding the rapidly developing climate emergency is the critical issue of this decade. At the 2015 United Nations Climate Change Conference (COP 21) held in Paris, the parties agreed on the long-term target of "holding the increase in the global average temperature to well below 2°C above pre-industrial levels and to pursue efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels [...]". In order to achieve this goal, a "global peaking of greenhouse gas emissions" should be reached "as soon as possible", with "rapid reductions thereafter" towards an essentially carbon-neutral global society and economy in the second half of the 21st century (UNFCCC 2015). This can only be achieved through substantial contributions by all sectors generating greenhouse gas emissions, including international aviation, one of the hardest sectors to decarbonize (along with industrial manufacturing).

Carbon-Neutral Fuel, Jet A-1

The strategy used for the Hawai'i project recognizes the interlinked, standardized, and slow-moving nature of the aviation sector. Rather than calling for new varieties of aircraft to be developed, with futuristic fuels requiring new infrastructure, our strategy is to create a drop-in carbon-neutral fuel which can be distributed and used within the existing aviation architecture. The system envisaged for Hawai'i is a drop-in solution, requiring no changes to engineering or operational systems for the industry. Our product is simple: Jet A-1, manufactured from atmospheric carbon, water, and green energy – not fossils or biogenic sources.

The preferred pathway to carbon-neutral fuel is the Fischer-Tropsch pathway, first developed by German

scientists in 1925. The feedstock is CO₂, which is over-abundant in the atmosphere, water, in order to arrive at hydrogen; and clean energy. Two sources of CO₂ are readily available in Hawai'i:

- **Point Sources**, such as the Kahe Point oil-burning electrical plant, which emits 1 megaton of CO₂ every year, or roughly 80% of the necessary carbon feedstock to decarbonize all interstate and international flights in Hawai'i; and
- **Direct Air Capture (DAC)** of CO₂ from ambient air.

Capture of CO₂ at a flue stack is less-expensive and stands out as a clear target for emissions reduction. Our approach is to treat each point source within the Hawai'ian Islands as a potential target, and to pursue a pathway for decarbonization for each.

However, there are several risk factors for these point sources. We would not want the carbon capture opportunity to be used politically as an argument to keep these facilities operating past their projected lifespans. Each flue stack also has its own mix of emissions. A waste-to-energy plant, for example, could spew out a range of heavy metals and toxins, whereas an oil-burning plant would have a relatively standardized emissions profile. Significantly, and potentially the source of a number of barriers to progress, carbon-capture agreements would require partnership with a variety of owners and operators — each with their own appetite for such partnerships – as well as the assent of regulators.

By contrast, a direct air capture machine, such as those designed and marketed by Climeworks or Carbon Engineering, would capture CO₂ from ambient air (Figure D2). This technology - now nearly 60 years old - allows for the pollutant to be recycled indefinitely, as it is captured and used for a number of commercial products (in our case Jet A-1), and then burned and released back into the atmosphere, and then collected again.

Although it is a new field of commercial endeavor, we have several options for technology partners.

- Klaus Lackner, regarded as the pioneer of the Direct Air Capture field, has recently commercialized his research via an Irish startup, Silicon Kingdom.
- Canadian firm Carbon Engineering, with very significant support from Bill Gates, built the first 'large' demo plant in 2016, capable of capturing 0.5 kilotons of CO₂ annually,
- Climeworks, based in Switzerland, delivered the world's first commercial DAC plant with a capacity of 0.9 kilotons per year in 2017.

Costs are estimated in the \$100-200/ton CO₂ range. For the Hawai'i commercial plant, we estimate a direct air capture facility with an annual capacity of 1.25 megatons of CO₂.

Figure D2. The Swiss start-up Climeworks has a modular direct air capture plant that draws in air with fans, captures CO₂ on the surface of a selective filter material, and releases the CO₂ to be stored or used as a raw material.

Hydrogen

As a “fleet of islands” in the Pacific, it is logical to take advantage of wave energy in order to solve for the high-energy requirements of hydrogen production, which is roughly 80% of the 300 megawatt of electricity needed for this plant. This approach would overcome the intermittency problems associated with conventional renewable energy sources such as solar and wind because hydrogen, once delivered to shore, can be stored in inexpensive tanks (much like oil or natural gas) and used on-demand for a wide range of applications, including grid power, transportation fuels, and fertilizer production.

An oceanic energy approach for hydrogen production lands in a cost range between \$1/kilogram and \$4.50/kilogram depending on the marine region where wave-generated hydrogen is deployed. In Hawai‘ian waters, costs of \$3.80/kilogram are projected initially, with reductions to \$2.80/kilogram expected over a period of 5-10 years, which would allow the final fuel product to be cost-competitive with fossil fuels.

Carbon Monoxide

With hydrogen from electrolysis and carbon dioxide from Direct Air Capture, we have the fundamental building blocks for processing Jet A-1, but one step remains. Carbon dioxide must be broken down into carbon monoxide. There are two approaches for this:

- A reverse water gas shift process, or a
- A new catalyst approach pioneered by Berkeley startup Opus 12.

Opus 12 takes the fundamental engineering of electrolysis but changes the catalyst material in order to perform work on the carbon dioxide molecule. A European firm, Sunfire, also has a catalyst approach which could work as an alternative.

Fischer–Tropsch Process

Once we have hydrogen and carbon monoxide, we have syngas (or “synthesis gas”), which is ready to move through the Fischer–Tropsch process. Weimar Germany had an abundance of coal, but needed liquid fuels. Franz Fischer and Hans Tropsch, research-

ers at the Kaiser Wilhelm Institute for Coal Research, obliged. Their eponymous process, at temperatures of 150–300 °C and pressures of one to several tens of atmospheres, converts syngas into a liquid hydrocarbon, which can be further refined through conventional means into a variety of fuels – diesel, automobile gasoline, waxes, and jet fuel.

Modularity, mass production, and political reality

Globally, we are aware of two other projects to develop commercial-scale power-to-liquid plants, both in Norway. For Hawai‘i, we anticipate completion by 2025. But throughout the world, we need to build hundreds, if not thousands of similar plants in order to successfully quench humanity’s desire for travel with a carbon-neutral fuel.

Modularity and mass production are thus essential. One startup has already begun to develop a containerized Fischer-Tropsch solution. We envision this approach being applied to the entire chain of production for carbon-neutral fuels.

The slowest element in this process, however, is the political reality of development – acquisition of real estate, permitting, local and regional council politics. As the era of fossil fuels comes to a close, it may make economic sense to retool abandoned oil rigs and tankers to become floating hydrogen, direct air capture, and fuel processing stations. This idea merits further exploration and investigation.

References

- Allison, EH, J Kurien, Y Ota et al. 2020. The Human Relationship with Our Ocean Planet. Washington, DC: World Resources Institute. <https://oceanpanel.org/blue-papers/HumanRelationshipwithOurOceanPlanet>
- Bennett, A., Patil, P., Kleisner, K., Rader, D., Virdin, J., and Basurto, X. (2018). Contribution of fisheries to food and nutrition security: Current knowledge, policy, and research. NI Report 18-02. Durham, NC: Duke University, <http://nicholasinstitute.duke.edu/publication>.
- Chanratchakool, P., and M.J. Phillips (2002) Social and economic impacts and management of shrimp disease among small-scale farmers in Thailand and Vietnam. p. 177-189. In: J.R. Arthur, M.J. Phillips, R.P. Subasinghe, M.B. Reantaso and I.H. MacRae. (eds.) Primary Aquatic Animal Health Care in Rural, Small-scale, Aquaculture Development. FAO Fish. Tech. Pap. No. 406.
- Conca, James (2020) "Managers of \$40 trillion make plans to decarbonize the world"
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/jamesconca/2020/09/07/managers-of-40-trillion-make-plans-to-decarbonize-the-world/#37ca-d12a5471>
- Congressional Research Services. 2017. Rare Earth Elements in National Defense: Background, Oversight Issues, and Options for Congress. <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/natsec/R41744.pdf>
- Costello, C., Cao, L., Gelcich, S. et al. (2020) "The future of food from the sea" *Nature*, 588, 95–100 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2616-y>
- Diallo, Mamadou S., Madhusudhana Rao Kotte, and Manki Cho. 2015. "Mining Critical Metals and Elements from Seawater: Opportunities and Challenges." *Environmental Science & Technology*, April 20, 49 (16), pp 9390–9399. DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.5b00463. <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/abs/10.1021/acs.est.5b00463>.
- Dickson, Giles, WindEurope, <https://windeurope.org/>
- Dvorak, Michael J., Cristina L. Archer, Mark Z. Jacobson. California offshore wind energy potential. *Renewable Energy* 35 (2020) 1244-1254. December 9, 2009. <https://web.stanford.edu/group/efmh/jacobson/Articles/I/Offshore/DvorakRenewEn2010.pdf>
- FAO (2018). Fishery aquaculture and statistics (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations). Rome: FAO. <http://www.fao.org/fishery/statistics/global-aquaculture-production/en>
- Folke, C., T. Hahn, P. Olsson, J. Norberg (2005) "Adaptive governance of social-ecological systems," *Annu. Rev. Environ. Resour.*, 30, 441-473.
- Gatsiounis, Ioannis (2008) In Thailand, pollution from shrimp farms threatens a fragile environment, *The New York Times*, <https://www.nytimes.com/2008/03/20/business/worldbusiness/20iht-rbogcoast.1.11278833.html>
- Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC) Global Off-shore wind report, 2020, https://gwec.net/wp-content/uploads/dlm_uploads/2020/08/GWEC-offshore-wind-2020-5.pdf
- High Level Panel for a Sustainable Ocean Economy (2020) Transformations for a sustainable ocean economy. <https://www.oceanpanel.org/ocean-action/files/transformations-sustainable-ocean-economy-eng.pdf>
- Haugan, P.M., L.A. Levin, D. Amon, M. Hemer, H. Lily and F.G. Nielsen. 2020. What Role for Ocean-Based Renewable Energy and Deep Seabed Minerals in a Sustainable Future? Washington, DC: World Resources Institute. www.oceanpanel.org/blue-papers/ocean-energy-and-mineral-sources.
- Huckerby, J., H. Jeffrey, A. de Andres, L. Finlay. 2016. An International Vision for Ocean Energy. Version III. Published by the Ocean Energy Systems Technology Collaboration Programme. <https://www.ocean-energy-systems.org>.
- International Energy Agency Technology Collaboration Program for Ocean Energy Systems. 2015. International Levelised Cost of Energy (LCOE) for Ocean Energy Technologies. <https://www.ocean-energy-systems.org/publications/oes-documents/market-policy-/document/international-levelised-cost-of-energy-for-ocean-energy-technologies-2015-/>.
- IEA (2019) Offshore Wind Outlook 2019, IEA, Paris <https://www.iea.org/reports/offshore-wind-outlook-2019>
- IRENA (2018) "Hydrogen from renewable power", International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2018/Sep/IRENA_Hydrogen_from_renewable_power_2018.pdf
- IRENA (2019) "Innovation landscape for a renewable powered-future: Solutions to integrate variable renewables", International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, www.irena.org/publications/2019/Feb/Innovation-landscape-for-a-renewable-powered-future.
- Kerr, S., J. Colton, K. Johnson, G. Wright (2015) "Rights and ownership in sea country: implications of marine renewable energy for indigenous and local communities," *Mar. Policy*, 52, 108-115, 10.1016/j.ijome.2014.12.001
- Kittner, N., Lil, F., and Daniel M. Kammen (2017) "Energy storage deployment and innovation for the clean energy transition," *Nature Energy*, 2, 17125. DOI: 10.1038/nenergy.2017.125
- Klaina, Sarah C., Terre Satterfield, Suzanne MacDonald Nicholas Battista, Kai M.A. Chan (2017) "Will communities "open-up" to offshore wind? Lessons learned from New England islands in the United States", *Energy Research & Social Sciences*, 34, 13 – 26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.05.009>
- Lange, M., Page, G. and Valerie Cummins (2018) "Governance challenges of marine renewable energy developments in the U.S. – Creating the enabling conditions for successful project development," *Marine Policy*, 90, 37-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.01.008>
- Lester, S., Stevens, J., Gentry, R., Kappel, C., Bell, T., Costello, C., & White, C. (2018a) "Marine spatial planning makes room for offshore aquaculture in crowded coastal waters," *Nature Communications*, 9(1), 945. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-03249-1>
- Lester, S., Gentry, R., Kappel, C., White, C., & Gaines, S. (2018b). Opinion: Offshore aquaculture in the United States: Untapped potential in need of smart policy. Proceedings of the

National Academy of Sciences, 115(28), 7162–7165. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1808737115>

Lester, S., Halpern, B., Grorud-Colvert, K., Lubchenco, J., Ruttenberg, B., Gaines, S., Airamé, S., & Warner, R. (2009) “Biological effects within no-take marine reserves: A global synthesis,” *Marine Ecology Progress Series*, 384, 33–46. <https://doi.org/10.3354/meps08029>

LiVecchi, A., A. Copping, D. Jenne, A. Gorton, R. Preus, G. Gill, R. Robichaud, R. Green, S. Geerlofs, S. Gore, D. Hume, W. McShane, C. Schmaus, H. Spence (2019) *Powering the Blue Economy; Exploring Opportunities for Marine Renewable Energy in Maritime Markets* (US Department of Energy, Office of Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy. Washington, D.C). <https://www.energy.gov/sites/prod/files/2019/09/f66/73355-v2.pdf>

Majumdar, A. 2015. ARPA-E FY 2013-FY2016 strategic vision roadmap. Presentation to the National Academy of Sciences Committee on the Evaluation of ARPA-E, Irvine, CA, December 8.

McKenna, P and Gearino, D (2019) “Government delays first big U.S. offshore wind farm. Is a double standard at play?” <https://insideclimatenews.org/news/19082019/vineyard-wind-offshore-renewable-energy-delay-boem-environmental-cumulative-review-nepa-massachusetts>

National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2017) *Valuing Climate Damages: Updating Estimation of the Social Cost of Carbon Dioxide*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. <https://doi.org/10.17226/24651>.

National Offshore Wind Strategy: Facilitating the Development of the Offshore Wind Industry in the United States. US Department of Energy and US Department of the Interior. <https://www.energy.gov/sites/prod/files/2016/09/f33/National-Offshore-Wind-Strategy-report-09082016.pdf>

Packard Foundation (2018). *Offshore finfish aquaculture: Global review and U.S. prospects*. Evaluation conducted by California Environmental Associates for the David & Lucile Packard Foundation.

Schubel, Jerry R and Kimberly Thompson (2019) “Farming the Sea: The Only Way to Meet Humanity’s Future Food Needs,” *GeoHealth*, 3(9), 238-244. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2019GH000204>

Searchinger, T, Waite, R, Hanson, C, & Ranganathan, J (2018). *World Resources Report: Creating a Sustainable Food Future, a Menu of Solutions to Feed Nearly 10 Billion People by 2050* (World Resources Institute). <https://www.wri.org/publication/creating-sustainable-food-future>

Sunter, DA, Murray, B, Lehman, M, Green, KB, Maushund, B, Kammen, DM (2017) “Two-stage Monte Carlo simulation to forecast levelized cost of electricity for wave energy,” 2017 IEEE 6th International Conference on Renewable Energy Research and Applications (ICRERA), San Diego, CA, 2017, pp. 638-641. DOI: 10.1109/ICRERA.2017.8191137

Wang, Yi-Hui , Ryan K Walter, Crow White, Matthew D Kehrl, Stephen F Hamilton, Patrick H Soper, and Benjamin I Ruttenberg. “Spatial and temporal variation of offshore wind power and its value along the Central California Coast:,” *Env. Research Comm.* (2019). <https://iopscience.iop.org/arti->

[cle/10.1088/2515-7620/ab4ee1#acknowledgements](https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7620/ab4ee1#acknowledgements).

Willett, W, Rockstrom, J, Loken, B, Springmann, M, Lang, T, Vermeulen, S, & Murray, C (2019) Food in the Anthropocene: the EAT-Lancet Commission on healthy diets from sustainable food systems. *The Lancet Commissions*, 393 (10170), 447 – 492. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)31788-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)31788-4)

Wiser, R & Millstein, D (2019) “Evaluating the economic return to public wind energy research and development in the United States,” *Applied Energy*, 261, 114449. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.114449>.

Working Group Lead & Members

Lead:

- Dan Kammen: Professor of Energy, University of California, Berkeley; Director of Renewable and Appropriate Energy Laboratory.

Members:

- Teresa Christopher: Principal at TRChristopher LLC; former White House Ocean Policy Advisor.
- Chip Fletcher: Associate Dean for Academic Affairs and Professor, Department of Earth Sciences, School of Ocean and Earth Science and Technology, University of Hawai'i.
- Michael Gerrard: Andrew Sabin Professor of Professional Practice and Director of the Sabin Center for Climate Change Law, Columbia Law School; Member and former Chair of the Faculty of Columbia's Earth Institute.
- Haunani Kane: NSF Research Fellow, University of Hawai'i at Hilo and School of Ocean and Earth Science and Technology.
- Heather Leslie: Director, Darling Marine Center, School of Marine Sciences, University of Maine.
- Jessica Reilly-Moman: PhD Student, Darling Marine Center, University of Maine.
- Ben Wolkon: Manager of Sustainable Investments, MUUS Investment Management, New York.
- Jack Chang: PhD Student, Energy & Resources Group, University of California, Berkeley.

WHAT WILL YOU DO?

The Blue Climate Initiative accelerates ocean-related strategies, collaborating across a multidisciplinary global community towards a restored and healthy climate; an understood and protected ocean; and resilient, thriving and equitable communities. The fiscal sponsor for the Blue Climate Initiative is Tetiaroa Society, a US 501(c)(3) nonprofit organization (tetiaroasociety.org).